

Computational Modeling of Expressive Music Performance: New Machine Learning Approaches for Dealing With Real-World Data

by

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Abstract

We present a doctoral pre-thesis report focusing of inductive computational modeling of music performance. We first introduce the expressive performance phenomenon from various points of view: musicology, music cognition, computer music and brain science. We then review the approaches for modeling this phenomenon with an emphasis on inductive models i.e. models built from real-world performance data. The process of building an expressive performance database from acoustical recording is explained. Then, we present a comparison of well-established data mining (DM) techniques for inducing models from this database. This comparison has several implications that show the limits of standard DM techniques for building expressive performance models. We then propose a new approach called Evolutionary Population of Generative Models (EPGM) based on Evolutionary Computation (EC) which is suitable for dealing with the issues that arise when using the standard DM paradigm for performance modeling. We introduce several strategies for biasing the model search towards useful solutions, and propose alternatives for evaluating the accuracy of the evolved models. We validate the results using the performance database presented above and study the impact of our design decisions. We discuss the potential implications this new method can have in the EC field. Finally, we present some conclusions and dress a proposal which has implications in both expressive music performance modeling, machine learning, and evolutionary computation fields.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In this work we present inductive modeling approaches to one of the most challenging aspects of computer music: modeling the knowledge applied by a musician when performing a score in order to produce an expressive performance of a piece.

Human music performance has been the scope of several studies for decades, a reason of this interest is probably because this phenomenon involves different aspects of human cognition. Music performance is fundamentally multimodal: if the perception of music is primarily based on the sense of audition, the performance of music gets involved much more aspects of human cognition such as senses of sight and touch, motor planning, memory, attention and emotion. Thus, music performance offers the opportunity to investigate several aspects of the human mind, and how they are related.

As an introduction to this topic, we will first present some evidence for psychology and brain research supporting that music performance is closely related to a wide range of phenomenon in human perception and cognition. We will then introduce the different modalities that have been employed to characterize expressivity in music performance. Finally, we will advance arguments supporting the usefulness of the computational approach for modeling expressive music performance.

1.1 Music performance as a part of music cognition

As shown by Peretz and Zatorre [2005], music performance includes a variety of tasks, such as playing or singing well-learned pieces from memory, sight reading, and improvisation. All these tasks combine rapid motor skills and relatively elaborate cognitive operations in addition to the processing of perceptual, memory, and emotional content. For instance, Cappelletti et al. [2000] demonstrates the existence of a visual-to-musical conversion subsystem in the brain. During performance, the musical processing areas are strongly connected to visual and motor areas. In [Peretz and Coltheart, 2003], a motor planning component for singing and playing is suggested as part of a modular architecture of musical processes. Haueisen and Knosche [2001] describe the involuntary motor activity observed in pianists as they listen to well-trained music, which suggests a tight coupling between input and output processes. The authors suggest this form of coupling might be involved in imitation and learning tasks.

These findings indicate that music performance should be seen as an epiphenomenon, consequently none of the brain processes involved in the music processing architecture mentioned above should be neglected. However, as pointed out by Peretz and Zatorre [2005], there are several obstacles hindering the unification of knowledge from brain science and lesion studies with other studies dealing with music performance. There is very little neuropsychological research on this issue, on the one hand because of the limited number of proficient musicians that suffered a brain damage, and on the other hand because of the difficulties of using neuroimaging techniques when studying motor behavior. New paradigms should be proposed to deal with these difficulties. Overall, if the researcher working in expressive music performance modeling has to be aware of the findings from music cognition and brain science, he can not merely rely on these findings when proposing approaches intended to model real-world performance.

We focus in this work on the *expressivity* - also referred as *expressiveness* or *expression* - which leads the performer to produce unique renditions of a musical excerpt. According to review presented by Timmers and Honing [2002], expressivity can be seen as the added value of a performance and is part of the reason why music sounds alive and is interesting to listen to. However, this definition remains vague and somewhat unsatisfactory. There

is no formal definition of musical expressivity. Instead, several aspects of expressivity have been proposed in the music performance literature.

1.2 Definitions of expressivity in music performance

- Expressivity as microstructure

The notion of microstructure [Repp, 1990, 1992; Palmer, 1997] in expressive music performance refers to the value added by the performer which is unspecified in a score. The microstructure consists of the large and small variations in timing, intensity, timbre and pitch [Palmer, 1997], and these variations are not necessarily related to the score. For instance, expressive intentions such as mood transformations can affect the microstructure of a performance (Canazza et al. [1997]).

- Expressivity as deviation from a musical score

Expressivity can be considered as a set of deviations that are applied to a mechanical rendition of the score. The mechanical rendition is called *nominal* melody. Seashore [1938] first observed that the human performance tended to deviate from the score. Gabrielsson [1974] analyzed in a more precise framework the deviations of rhythms that could be measured between a human performance and an hypothetical nominal rendition. Within this viewpoint the deviations usually considered are deviations of performance tempo, local timing, dynamics and insertion of pauses.

- Expressivity as deviation within a performance

Expressivity can also be seen as deviation from a mean performance (Desain and Honing [1991]), i.e. the mean performer behavior during the performance. This notion is useful for addressing the issue of microstructures (e.g. timbre) that are not explicitly linked to the score. It is also the basis of studies on the influence of performance tempo on an expressive rendition (see next section). According to Clarke [1995], the mean performance can be derived from common music practice.

We see at this point that each of these definitions reveal a particular aspect of music performance. We will see that if our approach has been pri-

marily motivated by the second viewpoint (i.e. deviation from the score), we have also considered the other viewpoints when completing our study. Consequently, rather than advocating for a specific definition, we prefer keeping all these possible viewpoints in mind.

1.3 Performance timing is not tempo invariant

Intuitively, it seems that performers are likely to produce different renditions depending on the performance tempo. One can figure out this by trying render a slow (60 beats per minute) and a fast version (e.g. 180 beats per minute) of a tune usually performed at 100 beats per minute. This raises the interesting question of whether the temporal aspects of performance scale uniformly when tempo changes. Are the timing deviation scaled to the target tempo still valid? In other words, does a uniformly time-stretched performance from the slow version to a fast tempo present the same expressive features than the fast performed version?

The Uniform Time Stretching (UTS) hypothesis claims that temporal aspects of performance scale uniformly with tempo changes Repp [1994]. UTS is used as a reference in the system presented in Grachten et al. [2006]. Further studies questioned the validity of such an hypothesis (see Timmers and Honing [2002]). Evidence from listening experiments presented by Honing [2006], as well as modeling experiments [Grachten et al., 2006] confirm the inappropriateness of the Uniform Time Stretch hypothesis.

1.4 Beyond note-to-note transformations

Analysis of performance have often been considered on a note to note basis, i.e. one note in the performance corresponds exactly to one note in the score. First, this can be explained because classical music has often been the object of performance studies. Also, from a computational modeling point of view, it is easier to handle pairwise comparisons (comparing sequentially pairs of score/performed note) than to consider more complex approaches. We first introduce the notion of grace notes and ornaments and then present a more complex hierarchy of *performance events* as defined in Grachten et al. [2006].

1.4.1 Grace notes and ornaments

Among the decisions musicians have to make when performing a musical, some decisions refer loosely to the score. This is the case when a performer inserts a grace note, a one or several note ornament that is not specified in the score, but is tightly related to the base note from which the ornaments are inserted. In classical music performance, insertions of grace notes have been often treated as errors. However, in other musical genres, insertions of grace notes and ornaments are more frequent [Timmers and Honing, 2002]. Grachten et al. [2003]; Ramirez et al. [2004] consider ornaments in jazz saxophone which is especially relevant because of the even looser relation between score notes and ornaments that prevails in jazz. By considering ornaments in a performance modeling framework, we get somehow closer to the ambiguous frontier that lies between music performance and improvisation. On the other hand, in some cases the score contains imprecise ornaments indications (marked with *tr* in classical music). In [Puiggròs et al., 2006], the authors investigate the modalities of such ornaments in classical bassoon performances.

1.4.2 A taxonomy of performance events

If ornaments are the more characteristic manifestation of performance events that go beyond note-to-note considerations, other performance events can take place if the performer is allowed to render a musical excerpt with some freedom. We now present the whole set of possible performance events below:

- Insertion
The occurrence of a performed note that is not in the score
- Deletion
The non-occurrence of a score note in the performance
- Consolidation
The agglomeration of multiple score notes into a single performed note
- Fragmentation
The performance of a single score note as multiple notes
- Transformation
The change of nominal note features like onset time, duration, pitch, microstructure, and dynamics
- Ornamentation
The insertion of one or several short notes to anticipate another performed note

Figure 1.1: A taxonomy of performance events (from Grachten et al. [2006])

Note the slight difference that exists between insertions (the inserted note is not related at all with the score), fragmentations (in which a note is split into several, but all the notes have the same pitch), and ornamentations (in which a score note is taken as a basis and is ornamented with one or several small notes). Symmetrically, a deletion removes a note from the score while a consolidation merges two notes in the performance. To summarize this we show below the performance events taxonomy as presented by Grachten et al. [2006].

We have presented an overview of different approaches aiming to define aspects of expressivity. As a summary, we acknowledge the growing evidence supporting performance as a tempo-dependent phenomenon. Also, if a complete view of expressivity in music performance can not ignore aspects such as timbre or notes microstructure, we prefer focusing on performance timing, performance events, and global note characteristics, such as mean note loudness. We will show in the conclusions how we plan to incorporate further expressive dimensions in the future.

Following we will introduce the usefulness of building computational models of expressive performance and cognition in general. We will then introduce the inductive approach for building computational models from real world data. Finally, we propose arguments for designing new machine learning techniques which would enable to address precisely the computational

performance modeling approach.

1.5 Computational modeling

We have seen in this introduction that expressive music performance is a complex phenomenon which has been the subject of investigation in a wide range of research areas such as musicology, psychology, neuroscience and cognitive science and that several data and tools have been proposed to investigate this manifestation of human brain modularity and interconnectedness. Consequently some question may arise in the reader's mind: Do we really need new tools or approaches to deal with music performance? Does a computational model will help us account better how the human brain works? We could respond by citing McClelland [2001] addressing the usefulness of computational modeling in cognitive neuroscience: "The key point is that an explicit computational perspective often leads to new ways of understanding observed phenomena that are apparently not always accessible to those who seek to identify subsystems without giving detailed consideration of the mechanisms involved". In other words, computational models may help us find the appropriate degree of abstraction necessary for observing the modularity of a phenomena.

On the other hand, it can be argued that the computational modeler is prone to integrate -often unconsciously- its very beliefs into a model representation. As a consequence, the model would be likely to exhibit the behavior expected by its creator. However, we can take advantage of this fact by using these prior beliefs as *alternatives*, and use the model for validating them. According to James McClelland, "The postulates built into the model need not represent the beliefs of the modeler; rather, they may represent a particular set of choices the modeler has made to try to gain insight into the model and, by proxy, the associated behavioral or biological phenomenon".

1.5.1 Inducing models from real world data

Therefore, computational models might contribute, by validating or contradicting specific theories and beliefs proposed by researchers of other areas, to accumulate evidence about expressive music performance. This can be seen as the *top-down* aspect of the present research. Conversely, we also have to address the fact that, apart from specific hypotheses and beliefs that

can be formulated about this phenomenon, most of the data describing music performance come from the performance itself. We then need to define approaches that will allow us to access and analyze this data in order to extract relevant information, this is the purpose of data mining and machine learning tools. From this we can build models that will reasonably fit and generalize this data. This represents the *bottom-up* aspect of our research.

1.5.2 A score-driven approach to performance modeling

As a first approach, we propose to investigate the modalities of score-driven approach to performance modeling. The problem can be stated as follows: how do underlying patterns in the score account for expressive transformations in a performance? The modeling task lies in finding an appropriate mapping from melodic descriptors to expressive features that reflects patterns appearing in a training set. Moreover, we are interested in a mapping that shows good generalization capabilities i.e. that produces accurate predictions when processing unseen data. This approach is a starting point towards building more elaborate models in which the score-driven component would interact with other processes.

1.5.3 On the usefulness of designing new machine learning techniques

Finally, we will see in this work that well established data mining techniques can be applied to the data extracted from human performance, and provide some interesting findings to the user. Most of these tools and algorithms are freely available, one of the most commonly used being the Weka¹ framework. However, the researcher may find difficult or impossible to implement specific hypotheses or top-down knowledge in these tools. Consequently there exists two alternatives to this which lies in (i) finding a techniques in the literature that suit best our needs (ii) developing new approaches for implementing new hypotheses. The research we present in this document can be seen as a tradeoff between these two directions.

¹www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka/

1.6 Outline of this document

Based on the ideas presented in this chapter, we present the outline of this work. Chapter 2 presents some related work in computational modeling of music performance. Chapter 3 shows the different components we used for building an expressive performance database from monophonic saxophone recordings of jazz standards and highlights some issues that arose during the building process. Chapter 4 introduces a collection of standard data mining techniques as well as state of the art relational learners we used to induce models reflecting some aspects of the timing of the performance database, and presents a comparison of these different approaches. In Chapter 5 we suggest that evolutionary approaches can be used for dealing with expressive performance inductive modeling. We thus present a novel learning algorithm, called Evolutionary Population of Generative Models (EPGM), which has been designed in order to overcome the limitations that characterize the other approaches for this problem. Then, we present in Chapter 6 some preliminary results obtained with the EPGM approach. We study the impact of several design decisions in the accuracy of this algorithm for different learning tasks. Finally, in Chapter 7, we discuss the overall approach presented in this work and present a work plan. The work directions are two-fold: first we define directions for improving and extending the EPGM approach. Then, we propose some extensions which are specific to expressive performance modeling. Some of these extensions can be handled within EPGM while others will require further investigations.

Chapter 2

Context of the present research

In this chapter, we summarize the studies completed for building computational models of expressive music performance. We present both manually devised approaches such as expert systems and inductive approaches to achieve this.

2.1 Overview of related efforts

2.1.1 Expert systems

There are a number of approaches which have addressed expressive performance without using data mining techniques. One of the first attempts to provide a computer system with musical expressiveness is that of Johnson [1992]. Johnson developed a rule-based expert system to determine expressive tempo and articulation for Bach's fugues from the *well-tempered clavier*. The rules were obtained from two expert performers.

A long-term effort in expressive performance modeling is the work of the KTH group (see Friberg [1997]; Bresin [2000]; Friberg et al. [2000]). Their *Director Musices* system incorporates rules for tempo, dynamics and articulation transformations. The rules are obtained from both theoretical musical knowledge, and experimentally from training using an analysis-by-synthesis approach. The rules are divided into *differentiation rules* which enhance the differences between scale tones, *grouping rules* which specify what tones belong together, and *ensemble rules* which synchronize the voices in an ensemble.

Canazza et al. [1997] developed a system to analyze the relationship between the musician's expressive intentions and his performance. The analysis reveals two expressive dimensions, one related to energy (dynamics), and another one related to kinetics (rubato). This leads to the definition of a Kinematics Energy space for music performance.

Dannenberg et al. [1998] investigated trumpet articulation transformations using (manually generated) rules. They developed a trumpet synthesizer which combines a physical model with an expressive performance model. The performance model generates control information for the physical model using a set of rules manually extracted from the analysis of a collection of performance recordings.

2.1.2 Inducing performance models from real-world data

As presented above, inductive performance modeling aims to induce computational models from a performance database. Furthermore accurate models should be able to generalize well on different data. One can consider using this approach for two purposes: knowledge discovery and performance rendering. We present these two aims below.

- Knowledge Discovery

Knowledge discovery refers to the process of building a model that is simple enough to be understood. In this case the predictions of the model do not need to be fine grained, what counts is the generality and the simplicity of the predictions. Knowledge discovery is often achieved using rule-based algorithms.

- Performance Rendering

In that case one can use numerical methods induce expressive performance models capable of *endowing* a computer generated music performance with the expressiveness that characterizes human generated music, i.e. transforming an inexpressive description of a musical piece into an expressive performance of the piece.

Previous research addressing expressive music performance using data mining techniques has included a broad spectrum of music domains. For instance, the problem of style recognition (e.g. recognition of lyrical or syncopated performances) using these techniques is addressed by Dannenberg

et al. [1997]. Mion and De Poli [2004] uses the Kinematics Energy Space as the basis for defining and recognizing expressive intentions (e.g. sad, light) from audio recordings. In these works, the relation between the score and the resulting performance is not considered, rather the research focus on a description of the performances.

The most related work to the research presented here is the work by Lopez de Mantaras and Arcos [2002], which was extended by Grachten et al. [2006] to build expressivity-aware tempo transformation system. Lopez de Mantaras et al report on SaxEx, a performance system capable of generating expressive solo performances in jazz. Their system is based on case-based reasoning, a type of analogical reasoning where problems are solved by reusing the solutions of similar, previously solved problems. In order to generate expressive solo performances, the case-based reasoning system retrieves, from a memory containing expressive interpretations, those notes that are *similar* to the input inexpressive notes. The case memory contains information about metrical strength, note duration, and so on, and uses this information to retrieve the appropriate notes.

With this exception, most of the research in expressive performance using data mining techniques has focused on classical piano music where the tempo of the performed pieces is not constant. Thus, in these works the authors have focused on global tempo and energy transformations while we are interested in note-level timing (i.e. note onset and duration deviations) and energy transformations.

Widmer [2002b,a] reported on the task of discovering general rules of expressive classical piano performance from real performance data via inductive machine learning. The performance data used for the study are MIDI recordings of 13 piano sonatas by W.A. Mozart performed by a skilled pianist. In addition to these data, the music score was also coded. The resulting substantial data consists of information about the nominal note onsets, duration, metrical information and annotations. When trained on the data an inductive rule learning algorithm discovered a small set of quite simple classification rules [Widmer, 2002b] that predict a large number of the note-level choices of the pianist.

Tobudic and Widmer [2003] describe a relational instance-based approach to the problem of learning to apply expressive tempo and dynamics variations to a piece of classical music, at different levels of the phrase hierarchy. At each hierarchical level, a second order polynomial approximation of both tempo and dynamics is computed. An illustration of this multilevel approximation

Figure 2.1: Multilevel decomposition of dynamics curve of performance of Mozart Sonata K.279:1:1, mm.31-38.: original dynamics curve plus the second-order polynomial shapes giving the best fit at four levels of phrase structure. The hierarchical phrase structure of this passage is indicated by four levels of brackets at the bottom of the figure.(from Tobudic and Widmer [2003])

for dynamics is shown in Figure 2.1.

The different phrases of a piece and the relations among them are represented in first-order logic. The description of the musical scores through predicates (e.g. *contains(ph1,ph2)*) provides the background knowledge. The training examples are encoded by another predicate whose arguments encode information about the way the phrase was played by the musician. Their learning algorithm recognizes similar phrases from the training set and applies their expressive patterns to a new piece.

We have followed a similar approach for building performance models for predicting either local timing and loudness, generation of ornaments, or note envelope shape in saxophone performances [Ramirez and Hazan, 2006; Ramirez et al., 2005a,b]. We have focused in obtaining readable models for understanding performance as well as generative model from rendering new performances based on the training data.

Other inductive approaches to rule learning in music and musical analysis include Dovey [1995], Van Baelen and De Raedt [1996], Morales [1997] and Igarashi et al. [2002]. Dovey [1995] analyzes piano performances of Rachmaniloff pieces using inductive logic programming and extracts rules underlying them. Van Baelen and De Raedt [1996] extended Dovey's work

and attempted to discover regularities that could be used to generate MIDI information derived from the musical analysis of the piece. Morales [1997] reports research on learning counterpoint rules. The goal of the reported system is to obtain standard counterpoint rules from examples of counterpoint music pieces and basic musical knowledge from traditional music. Igarashi et al. [2002] describe the analysis of respiration during musical performance by inductive logic programming. Using a respiration sensor, respiration during cello performances was measured and rules were extracted from the data together with musical/performance knowledge such as harmonic progression and bowing direction.

2.2 Summary

We have presented in this section a review of approaches to computational modeling of expressive music performance. On the one hand, an approach lies in building rule systems which are manually devised by experts, the most characteristic example being KTH *Director Musices*. The second type of approach uses data mining algorithms in order to induce computational models of performance based on empirical data, i.e. a performance database. Among all the inductive works presented here, the tasks lies in predicting some particular aspect of the performance (i.e. duration ratio or tempo deviation). The work presented in this document has been motivated by these contributions. However, we will see in 4 that we face some limitations when applying data mining techniques in the context of real world performance. Prior to this, we will explain in Chapter 3 the process of building a database from a set of acoustic recordings in order to process the resulting data with inductive approaches.

Chapter 3

Building the database

We show in this chapter how we completed the acquisition of the expressive performance database we use in this report. We first list the musical material that was chosen, and how the performances were recorded. Then, we show how we extracted a symbolic transcription of these monophonic recordings and how we achieved the alignment of the performance transcriptions with the score. Finally we highlight some common issues we face when dealing with this type of data.

3.1 Musical material

The training data used in our experimental investigations are monophonic recordings of four Jazz standards from the *New Real Book* (*Body and Soul*, *Once I loved, Like Someone in Love* and *Up Jumped Spring*) performed by a professional saxophonist at 11 different tempos around the nominal tempo. For each piece, the nominal tempo was determined by the musician as the most natural and comfortable tempo to interpret the piece. Also, for each piece, the musician identified the fastest and slowest tempos at which a piece could be reasonably interpreted. Interpretations were recorded at regular intervals around the nominal tempo (5 faster and 5 slower) within the fastest-slowest tempo limits. The resulting data set is composed of 4360 performed notes extracted from more than two hours of audio recordings.

Figure 3.1: Overview of the data acquisition system

3.2 Acquiring the data

In this section, we present the whole data acquisition process which is implemented to build an expressive performance database from monophonic audio signals. We give an overview of the acquisition process in Figure 3.1.

In this figure, both data and processes are appearing. The data are drawn with ellipses while the processes are drawn with boxes. The input data is made of pairs of [audio performance recording, score]. Corresponding to these pairs we obtain as an output of the processes the triplets [target melody, performance events, melodic context features]. Most of the modeling approaches focus on the pair [performance events, melodic context features] for building performance models. We will show in Section 5.3.2 that the approach we developed can also build models based on the pair [target melody, melodic context features], that is, without referring directly to the performance events.

The processes of the data acquisition step are the following: (i) Transcription from monophonic audio signals, (ii) Alignment of the transcribed performances with the score and (iii) Melodic feature extraction from the

nominal score. They are presented below.

3.2.1 Transcription from monophonic audio signals

In this subsection, we summarize how we extract a symbolic description from the monophonic recordings of Jazz standards performances. We need this symbolic representation in order to apply data mining techniques to the data.

First, we show how to compute the instantaneous fundamental frequency of the recordings. Then, we perform a temporal segmentation of the signal into notes based on both instantaneous fundamental frequency and energy. The method we summarize here was initially presented by Gómez [2002].

3.2.1.1 Algorithms for feature extraction

Figure 3.2 represents the steps that are performed to obtain a melodic description from audio. First of all, we perform a spectral analysis of a portion of sound, called analysis frame, whose size is a parameter of the algorithm. This spectral analysis lies in multiplying the audio frame with an appropriate analysis window and performing a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) to obtain its spectrum. In this case, we use a frame width of 46 ms, an overlap factor of 50%, and a Keiser-Bessel 25dB window. Then, we perform a note segmentation using low-level descriptor values. Once the note boundaries are known, the note descriptors are computed from the low-level and the fundamental frequency values.

3.2.1.2 Low-level descriptors computation

The main low-level descriptors used to characterize expressive performance are instantaneous energy and fundamental frequency.

3.2.1.2.1 Energy computation The energy descriptor is computed on the spectral domain, using the values of the amplitude spectrum at each analysis frame. In addition, energy is computed in different frequency bands as defined by Klapuri [1999], and these values are used by the algorithm for note segmentation.

Figure 3.2: Block diagram of the melody descriptor

3.2.1.2.2 Fundamental frequency estimation For the estimation of the instantaneous fundamental frequency we use a harmonic matching model derived from the Two-Way Mismatch procedure (TWM) [Maher and Beauchamp, 1994]. For each fundamental frequency candidate, mismatches between the harmonics generated and the measured partials frequencies are averaged over a fixed subset of the available partials. A weighting scheme is used to make the procedure robust to the presence of noise or absence of certain partials in the spectral data. The solution presented in [Maher and Beauchamp, 1994] employs two mismatch error calculations. The first one is based on the frequency difference between each partial in the measured sequence and its nearest neighbor in the predicted sequence. The second is based on the mismatch between each harmonic in the predicted sequence and its nearest partial neighbor in the measured sequence. This two-way mismatch helps to avoid octave errors by applying a penalty for partials that are present in the measured data but are not predicted, and also for partials whose presence is predicted but which do not actually appear in the measured sequence. The TWM mismatch procedure has also the benefit that the effect of any spurious components or partial missing from the measurement can be counteracted by the presence of uncorrupted partials in the same frame. Figure 3.3 shows the

Figure 3.3: Flow diagram of the TWM algorithm

block diagram for the fundamental frequency estimator following a harmonic-matching approach.

First, we perform a spectral analysis of all the windowed frames, as explained above. Secondly, the prominent spectral peaks of the spectrum are detected from the spectrum magnitude. These spectral peaks of the spectrum are defined as the local maxima of the spectrum which magnitude is greater than a threshold. The spectral peaks are compared to a harmonic series and a two-way mismatch (TWM) error is computed for each fundamental frequency candidates. The candidate with the minimum error is chosen to be the fundamental frequency estimate.

After a first test of this implementation, some improvements to the original algorithm were implemented to deal with some errors of the algorithm:

- Peak selection: a peak selection routine has been added in order to eliminate spectral peaks corresponding to noise. The peak selection is done according to a masking threshold around each of the maximum magnitude peaks. The form of the masking threshold depends on the peak amplitude, and uses three different slopes depending on the frequency distance to the peak frequency.

- Context awareness: we take into account previous values of the fundamental frequency estimation and instrument dependencies to obtain a more adapted result.
- Noise gate: a noise gate based on some low-level signal descriptor is applied to detect silences, so that the estimation is only performed in non-silent segments of the sound.

3.2.1.3 Note segmentation

Note segmentation is performed using a set of frame descriptors, which are energy computation in different frequency bands and fundamental frequency. Energy onsets are first detected following a band-wise algorithm that uses some psycho-acoustical knowledge [Klapuri, 1999]. In a second step, fundamental frequency transitions are also detected. Finally, both results are merged to find the note boundaries (onset and offset information).

3.2.1.4 Note descriptor computation

We compute note descriptors using the note boundaries and the low-level descriptors values. The low-level descriptors associated to a note segment are computed by averaging the frame values within this note segment. Pitch histograms have been used to compute the pitch note and the fundamental frequency that represents each note segment, as found in [McNab et al., 1996]. This is done to avoid taking into account mistaken frames in the fundamental frequency mean computation.

First, frequency values are converted into cents, by the following formula:

$$c = 1200 \cdot \frac{\log\left(\frac{f}{f_{ref}}\right)}{\log 2} \quad (3.1)$$

where $f_{ref} = 8.176$. Then, we define histograms with bins of 100 *cents* and hop size of 5 *cents* and we compute the maximum of the histogram to identify the note pitch. Finally, we compute the frequency mean for all the points that belong to the histogram.

The MIDI pitch is computed by quantization of this fundamental frequency mean over the frames within the note limits.

3.2.2 Alignment of the transcriptions with the score

In this section we describe a technique used to derive automatically an alignment between the symbolic performance transcription with the score nominal melody. The outcome of the alignment process is a sequence of transformation events. We will see that this sequence of transformations will basically form the targets for the training data used in the data mining algorithms presented in Chapter 4. However, it is possible to build a performance model without directly considering this sequence of transformations as the training target (see Chapter 5). In such a case, this preliminary alignment process is no longer necessary. The symbolic alignment process we summarize here has been presented by Grachten et al. [2003]. It is mainly based on the computation of the edit-distance between the nominal score and the performance transcription.

3.2.2.1 Edit distance computation

The edit-distance [Levenshtein, 1966] is used to determine the similarity between two performances of the same melody. It is defined as the minimal total cost of a sequence of editions needed to transform one performance into the other, given the edit-operations deletion, insertion, and replacement. The edit-distance is flexible enough to accommodate for comparison of sequences of different lengths (in case of e.g. consolidation/fragmentation) and it allows for easy customization to a particular use by adjusting parameter values of the edit-operation cost functions. The cost of a particular edit-operation is defined through a *cost function* w for that operation, that computes the cost of applying that operation to the notes of the source and target sequences that were given as parameters to w . We defined the following cost functions for 1-0, 0-1, 1-1, N-1, and 1-N edit-operations, which we write respectively $w(\mathbf{s}_i, \emptyset)$, $w(\emptyset, \mathbf{t}_j)$, $w(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{t}_j)$, $w(\mathbf{s}_{i-K:i}, \mathbf{t}_j)$ and $w(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{t}_{j-L:j})$.

$$\begin{aligned}
w(\mathbf{s}_i, \emptyset) &= \alpha_1 (\delta \mathcal{D}(s_i) + \epsilon \mathcal{E}(s_i)) + \beta_1 \\
w(\emptyset, \mathbf{t}_j) &= \alpha_1 (\delta \mathcal{D}(t_j) + \epsilon \mathcal{E}(t_j)) + \beta_1 \\
w(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{t}_j) &= \alpha_2 \left(\begin{array}{l} \pi | \mathcal{P}(s_i) - \mathcal{P}(t_j) | + \\ \delta | \mathcal{D}(s_i) - \mathcal{D}(t_j) | + \\ o | \mathcal{O}(s_i) - \mathcal{O}(t_j) | + \\ \epsilon | \mathcal{E}(s_i) - \mathcal{E}(t_j) | \end{array} \right) + \beta_2 \\
w(\mathbf{s}_{i-K:i}, \mathbf{t}_j) &= \alpha_3 \left(\begin{array}{l} \pi \sum_{k=0}^K | \mathcal{P}(s_{i-k}) - \mathcal{P}(t_j) | + \\ \delta | \mathcal{D}(t_j) - \sum_{k=0}^K \mathcal{D}(s_{i-k}) | + \\ o | \mathcal{O}(s_{i-K}) - \mathcal{O}(t_j) | + \\ \epsilon \sum_{k=0}^K | \mathcal{E}(s_{i-k}) - \mathcal{E}(t_j) | \end{array} \right) + \beta_3 \\
w(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{t}_{j-L:j}) &= \alpha_3 \left(\begin{array}{l} \pi \sum_{l=0}^L | \mathcal{P}(s_i) - \mathcal{P}(t_{j-l}) | + \\ \delta | \mathcal{D}(s_i) - \sum_{l=0}^L \mathcal{D}(t_{j-l}) | + \\ o | \mathcal{O}(s_i) - \mathcal{O}(t_{j-L}) | + \\ \epsilon \sum_{l=0}^L | \mathcal{E}(s_i) - \mathcal{E}(t_{j-l}) | \end{array} \right) + \beta_3
\end{aligned}$$

Where $\mathbf{s}_i = \langle s_i \rangle$, and $\mathcal{P}(s_i)$, $\mathcal{D}(s_i)$, $\mathcal{O}(s_i)$, and $\mathcal{E}(s_i)$ respectively represent the pitch, duration, onset, and dynamics attributes of a note s_i . Each attribute has a corresponding parameter (π , δ , o , and ϵ , respectively), that controls the impact of that attribute on operation costs. The β parameters control the absolute cost of the operations. The α parameters control the partial cost of the operation due to (differences in) attribute values of the notes.

3.2.2.2 Distribution of performance events

As a result of the alignment process, we obtained the following number of performance events, as shown in Table 3.1. Note that a vast majority of the extracted events are transformations events (92.12% of all the performance events). The other performance events are present in a much lower proportion: consolidation events (0.18%), ornamentation events (0.08%), fragmentation-events (0.08%), insertion events (0.03%) and deletion events (0.01%).

We have presented the first two parts of our system, namely the transcription component and the alignment component. As an outcome of these processes we obtain the *targets* -whether they describe the performance melody or the sequence of performance events- which we will use in the training database. On the other hand, we want to relate these targets with the melodic

Type of event	Occurrences
Transformation	3848
Ornamentation	36
Fragmentation	36
Consolidation	76
Insertion	14
Deletion	9

Table 3.1: Occurrences of each type of performance event in the database

context of the score, in order to build models which predict, for a significant number of cases, how a particular note in a particular context should be played. In our system, aspects of the melodic context can be considered as *input features*. We present below the melodic features we considered.

3.2.3 Extraction of the melodic context features

We explain here the melodic analysis process we developed to represent the nominal score context. Firstly, we are aware of the fact that not all the expressive transformations performed by a musician can be predicted at a local note level. Musicians perform music considering a number of abstract structures (e.g. musical phrases) which makes of expressive performance a multi-level phenomenon. In this context, our aim is to obtain an integrated model of expressive performance which combines local note context features with structure-level features.

Conversely, most of the well established data mining algorithms used in the literature (see Chapter 4) are *propositional*, consequently they operate on fixed-size vectors. However, we will see that representing several levels of abstractions of the melodic context into such a fixed-size vector is a quite difficult task, mainly because musical structures can be ambiguous and have no clear boundaries.

Therefore, we propose the following approach: As a first step, a fix-length set of local melodic features is considered, we refer to Local Note Context features. This set of features can be used with any standard data mining algorithms. Then, we provide a two-fold extension of this first representation. To achieve this we represent the melodic context in a *relational* way. This representation is defined in First Order Logic, a substantially more expres-

sive representation than the traditional propositional rules used in most rule learning algorithms, this will be detailed further in Section 4.3.

3.2.3.1 Local note context features

For each note, we consider number of attributes representing both properties of the note itself and some aspects of the musical context in which the note appears. Information about intrinsic properties of the note includes the note duration and the note metrical position, while information about its local context includes duration of previous and following notes, extension and direction of the intervals between the note and the previous and following notes. Finally, having in mind the considerations on the influence of tempo in performance presented in Section 1.3, we consider the tempo relative variation of the performance compared with the nominal tempo.

3.2.3.2 Extending the melodic context

On the one hand, the Local Note Context is temporally extended by accessing recursively the Local Note Context context of the neighboring notes. Indeed, it is possible to implement a recursive access to an arbitrary number of neighboring notes by defining a predicate specifying temporal relation of notes (e.g. successor, predecessor) in first order logic. We will come back to this issue in Section 4.3 On the other hand, a more abstract level based on Narmour Implication/Realization Model is also considered.

3.2.3.2.1 A first step towards a multi-level score representation: the Narmour I/R analysis The Implication/Realization model [Narmour, 1990] is a theory of perception and cognition of melodies. The theory states that a melodic musical line continuously causes listeners to generate expectations of how the melody should continue. The nature of these expectations in an individual are motivated by two types of sources: innate and learned. According to Narmour, on the one hand we are all born with innate information which suggests to us how a particular melody should continue. On the other hand, learned factors are due to exposure to music throughout our lives and familiarity with musical styles and particular melodies. According to Narmour, any two consecutively perceived notes constitute a melodic interval, and if this interval is not conceived as complete, it is an *implicative interval*, i.e. an interval that implies a subsequent interval with

Figure 3.4: Prototypical Narmour structures

Figure 3.5: Narmour analysis of *All of Me* (from Grachten et al. [2006])

certain characteristics. That is to say, some notes are more likely than others to follow the implicative interval. Two main principles recognized by Narmour concern *registral direction* and *intervallic difference*. The principle of registral direction states that small intervals imply an interval in the same registral direction (a small upward interval implies another upward interval and analogously for downward intervals), and large intervals imply a change in registral direction (a large upward interval implies a downward interval and analogously for downward intervals). The principle of intervallic difference states that a small (five semitones or less) interval implies a similarly-sized interval (plus or minus 2 semitones), and a large interval (seven semitones or more) implies a smaller interval. Based on these two principles, melodic patterns or groups can be identified that either satisfy or violate the implication as predicted by the principles. Such patterns are called structures and are labeled to denote characteristics in terms of registral direction and intervallic difference. Figure 3.4 shows prototypical Narmour structures. A note in a melody often belongs to more than one structure. Thus, a description of a melody as a sequence of Narmour structures consists of a list of overlapping structures. We parse each melody in the training data in order to automatically generate an implication/realization analysis of the pieces. Figure 3.5 shows the analysis for a melody fragment.

As pointed out by Grachten et al. [2006], The I-R analysis can be regarded as a moderately abstract representation of the score, that conveys information about the rough pitch interval contour, and through the boundary locations of the I-R structures, includes metrical and durational information of the melody as well.

We presented in this section three main components we use for building an expressive performance database. These components provides an automatic way of transcribing and aligning the performance recordings with the score. However, we faced different practical and methodological issues when building the performance database. We present and discuss these issues in next section.

3.3 Common issues

We highlighted three major issues when building the music performance database from the set of acoustical saxophone recordings presented in Section 3.1. Firstly, in some cases, we had to correct manually the output of the audio transcription and alignment components. Secondly, some excerpts where incompletely recorded. Finally, we had to deal with the variability of performances.

3.3.1 Manual corrections

Automatic transcription of melodies from audio signals is a difficult task. This is particularly true when considering brass signals, even if they are monophonic. For instance, the implementation proposed by Ricard [2005] which won the latest MIREX¹ onset detection contest on a solo-brass database yielded an average F-measure of 72.6%. In the case of saxophone signals, state of the art algorithms are not reliable enough to allow the user avoid manual corrections.

On the other hand, the automatic alignment of the transcribed performances with the score is also prone to error, although the system produces less alignment errors compared with the transcription component, and less correction work is needed in that case. This is also the result of a evolutionary optimization process presented in [Grachten et al., 2004], which yielded a gain of accuracy of 14%.

3.3.2 Incomplete and duplicated excerpts

As mentioned in Section 3.1, each tune was performed at 11 different tempi (five slower, one nominal tempo, and five faster tempo). This represents a

¹www.musir-ir.org/evaluation/mirex-results

considerable amount of recording time, namely more than two hours. This duration is done without counting the breaks and repetitions subsequent to mistakes introduced by the performer. Consequently, we can find in the final recordings some excerpts where parts are missing, while some parts of other excerpt are duplicated (i.e. a part of an excerpt performed with equal tempo is recorded twice). This latter point leads us to an interesting remark on performance variability we present below.

3.3.3 On the variability of performances

As a side-effect of the presence of duplicated recordings, we had the opportunity to investigate whether two similar recordings showed similar performance events. We have noticed that, if the performances were globally similar, they could vary at the note level (e.g. an ornamentation is made in only one version). Obviously, the melodic context of the two repeated excerpts is strictly the same. As a result, and having in mind that a pure score-driven approach could not handle this variability, we discarded the duplicated excerpts to keep only one version.

3.4 Summary

We have drawn in this chapter a detailed picture explaining the process of data acquisition from acoustic recordings of jazz saxophone. We presented the transcription, alignment, and score feature extraction components we use in this work. We finally showed the issues that arose when constituting the performance database. We will present in Chapter 4 our initial approach: we can apply both propositional and relational data mining techniques for building performance models focused on either knowledge discovery or performance rendering. We will then point out the issues that lead us to suggest a new approach for evolving populations of generative models (EPGM) in Chapter 5.

Chapter 4

Comparing data mining techniques

We report in this section the first modeling experiments we completed in order to compare standard data mining techniques. We first present the learning tasks we modeled, and then draw an overview of the algorithms we used. We first introduce *propositional* learners, i.e. algorithms which operate on examples represented in propositional logic. We then introduce *relational* rule learners. Finally we present and compare the results of these approaches, and discuss the overall data mining approach.

4.1 Learning tasks

We propose in this section two types of learning tasks. We refer to Section 1.4.2 and Table 3.1 for a presentation of the performance events and their occurrence in the performance database. The first learning task aims to predict the characteristics of a transformation event, i.e. a note-to-note transformation. We will see this task can be modeled with either classification or regression methods. The second learning task aims to predict which type of performance event will be associated to a score note. Thus, this second task is a classification task.

4.1.1 Task 1: Transformation event characterization

First, we want to predict the characteristics we extracted from the transformation events in the performance database. These measurements were only extracted from transformation-events i.e. situations where one performed note corresponds exactly to one score note. The main reason for this is because the main part of the performance events collected in the database are transformation events. For each transformation event in the database, we computed the following expressive measurements:

- Duration ratio: The ratio between the performed note and the nominal score note.
- Onset deviation: The temporal difference (expressed as a fraction of quarter note) between the performed note onset and the nominal score onset.
- Relative energy variation: The relative error between the note loudness and the average of the note loudness over the whole excerpt.

Note that the first two measures, namely duration ratio and onset deviation, are directly related to score. In that sense they describe the viewpoint defining expressivity as a deviation from the score (as defined in Section 1.2). Conversely the latter measure, namely energy relative variation, is not related to the score because there were no loudness indications in the nominal score. Rather, this measure uses as reference the mean note loudness of the excerpts. Consequently, this latter measure is related to the another definition of expressivity: expressivity as a deviation from the mean performance.

4.1.2 Task 2: Performance event type prediction

In this learning task, we induce models in order to predict which type of performance event is likely to be associated to a nominal score note. This is a classification task. We choose to restrict the possible outcome to the following classes: transformation event, ornamentation event, consolidation event and fragmentation event. We therefore discarded insertion events and deletion events because there was too few of such examples in the database (see Table 3.1)

We present below the different data mining algorithms we used in order to model these two tasks. We first present propositional learners and then

introduce relational learners. In both of these settings, we will see that tools are available to achieve either regression or classification tasks.

4.2 Propositional learners

We first introduce numerical prediction methods (i.e. regression algorithms) and then present classification approaches.

4.2.1 Numerical methods

- **Linear regression** is the simplest scheme for numeric prediction which has been widely used in statistical applications. The idea is to express the predicted value as a linear combination of the attributes, with pre-determined weights that are calculated from the training data, in order to minimize the overall deviation between the training values and the model.
- **Model trees** build an induction tree which has a different linear model on each leaf. Model trees behave well as each of the leaves' linear models approximates a set of more specific cases than with a global linear model, i.e. model trees approximate continuous functions by linear "patches", a more sophisticated representation than simple linear regression.
- **Support Vector Machines** take great advantage of using a non linear attribute mapping that leads them to be able to predict non-linear models (though they remain linear in a higher dimension space). Thus, they provide a more flexible prediction, but with a higher computational cost necessary to perform all the computations in the higher dimensional space. Training a Support Vector Machine requires the solution of a very large quadratic programming optimization problem. The quadratic programming resolution has been optimized in terms of speed and memory usage with the sequential minimal optimization algorithm Platt [1999]. They have been applied to numerical prediction Smola and Scholkopf [1999] and the results largely depend on the tuning of the algorithm, e.g. the choice of the kernel evaluation function and the parameters which control the amount up to which deviations

are tolerated (denoted by epsilon). The kernel function defines implicitly the higher dimensional mapping applied to the training vector. With an appropriate tuning, it is possible to control the number of support vectors that define a boundary between two classes. We were interested in obtaining a model with a relatively reduced number of support vectors (i.e. less than a third of the training instances) in order to avoid overfitting and thus have tuned empirically four support vector machines with the following parameters: (1) Linear kernel, $C=1$, $\text{epsilon}=0.05$, (2) 2nd order polynomial kernel, $C=1$, $\text{epsilon}=0.05$, (3) 3rd order polynomial kernel, $C=1$, $\text{epsilon}=0.05$, (4) Radial Basis Function kernel, $\text{gamma exponent}=0.95$, $C=10$, $\text{epsilon}=0.05$.

4.2.2 Discretization

A discretization step is needed in order to model Task 1 with classification algorithms. Consequently we discretized the input values into classes, and used classifiers in order to induce predictive models for duration ratio, onset deviation and energy variation. The number of classes was determined by the distribution of the input values. We applied a fix-width discretization for duration ratio and onset deviation with 9 and 7 classes, respectively. As mentioned earlier, the case of energy variation is quite different, thus we performed a frequency discretization i.e. each target class contains the same number of cases, and characterize soft, normal, and loud notes.

4.2.3 Classification methods

Following we report the classification methods we used in this study.

- The **naive Bayes classifier** is based on Bayes rule on conditional probability propagation. It is called “naive” because this rule assumes that the attributes of an instance are independent from each other. This can lead to weak results when attributes have a strong correlation. The algorithm implements redundant attributes filtering as preprocess Langley [1994]. Despite being one of the simplest algorithms, it has outperformed more complex techniques in a significant number of cases.
- **Lazy Methods** are based on the notion of lazy learning which subsumes a family of algorithms that store the complete set of given (classified) examples of an underlying example language and delay all further

calculations until requests for classifying yet unseen instances are received. The K-Nearest Neighbor algorithm, is one of the most popular instanced-based algorithm, which handles well noisy data if the training set has an acceptable size. The main idea of this algorithm is to compare a test set with its nearest neighbors (the number is determined by the user and the computational cost largely depends on it). A major problem of the simple approach of K-Nearest Neighbor is that the vector distance will not necessarily be suited for finding intuitively similar examples, especially if irrelevant attributes are present. We empirically found the best number of neighbors: 5 for the duration ratio model, 11 for the onset deviation model, and 1 for the energy variation model. KStar algorithms proceeds in a similar fashion as K-NN, but use an entropy similarity measure distance to find the neighbors of a test vector.

- **Tree induction algorithms** build a tree model by selecting at each node the most relevant attribute. We compare the results of C4.5 Quinlan [1990a, 1993], C4.5 with boosting, and the random forest algorithm. Boosting refers to a meta-algorithm that may improve the results of any classification algorithm by giving to each instance of the training set a particular weight proportional with the difficulty to classify such instance. That is, a first classification model is proposed giving the same weight to all the training instances. Misclassified instances with the model are then given a greater weight, and so on. After a user defined number of iterations (in our case 10 iterations) the resulting model is able to deal with “difficult” training instances. This boosting method can drastically improve the results of an inaccurate model, though overfitting can occur. The random forest algorithm uses a bagging technique: it combines the decision of different models amalgamating the various outputs in a single prediction. The decision can be seen as a vote between the models. Each tree is built using random features selection. We used 20 random trees in our test with the random forest algorithm.

All the algorithms presented below involve working on fixed-size feature vectors. Such algorithms can be seen as *propositional* because the induced models have the same expressive power as *propositional logic*. In many cases, propositional processes are sufficiently expressive to describe a concept accu-

rately. However, there are cases where more expressive rules, e.g. first-order logic rules, would provide a more intuitive concept description.

4.3 Relational learners: Inductive Logic Programming

These are cases where the knowledge to be learned is best expressed by allowing variables in attributes. One important special case involving learning sets of rules containing variables is called Inductive Logic Programming [Shapiro, 1983; Quinlan, 1990b].

4.3.1 First order logic representation

Inductive Logic Programming has proved to be an extremely well suited technique for learning expressive performance rules. This is mainly due to (1) the possibility of considering an arbitrary-size note context (not necessarily the context given by the previous and following note) without explicitly defining extra attributes, and (2) the possibility of introducing *background knowledge* (i.e. music theory knowledge) directly into the learning task.

The background knowledge is useful to guide the rule construction or to simply make rules more readable. Using the training data, we applied a standard Inductive Logic Programming sequential covering algorithm that incrementally constructs a theory as a set of first-order rules (Horn clauses) by learning new rules one at a time, removing the positive examples covered by the latest rule before attempting to learn the next rule.

We then defined the following target predicates: `duration/2`, `onset/2`, and `energy/2`. (where `/n` at the end of the predicate name refers to the predicate arity, i.e. the number of arguments the predicate takes). Each target predicate corresponds to a particular type of transformation: `duration/2` refers to duration transformation, `onset/2` to onset deviation, and `energy/2` to energy transformation. For each target predicate we use as example set the complete training data specialized for the particular type of transformation, e.g. for `duration/2` we used the complete data set information on duration transformation (i.e. the performed duration transformation for each note in the data set). The arguments are the note in the piece and performed transformation. We use (background) predicates to specify both note

musical context and background information. The predicates we consider include `context/6`, `narmour/2`, `succ/2` and `member/3`. Predicate `context/8` specifies the local context of a note as defined in Section 3.2.3.1. Predicate `narmour/2` specifies the Narmour groups to which the note belongs. Its arguments are the note identifier and a list of Narmour groups. Predicate `succ(X,Y)` means Y is the successor of X, and Predicate `member(X,L)` means X is a member of list L. Note that `succ(X,Y)` also mean X is the predecessor of Y. The `succ(X,Y)` predicate allows the specification of arbitrary-size note-context by chaining a number of successive notes:

$$succ(X_1, X_2), succ(X_2, X_3), \dots, succ(X_{n-1}, X_n)$$

where X_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) is the note of interest. The Inductive Logic Programming modeling experiments were conducted using the Aleph system Srinivasan [2001].

4.4 Baseline results

We report in this section the baselines we choose in the case of classification and regression tasks.

4.4.1 Classification baseline

As a first approach, we can use the results of a random classifier as baseline. Concerning Task 1, we discretized the duration ratio into 9 classes, the onset deviation into 7 classes, and the energy variation into 3 classes. In that case, the classification results presented in Section 4.5 are to be compared with the accuracy of a random classification i.e. 11.11% for duration ratio, 14.28% for onset deviation, and 33.33% for energy variation. Concerning Task 2, there are 4 target classes, namely transformation, consolidation, fragmentation and ornamentation. Consequently, the random classification baseline for this task is 25%. However, the random baseline results presented might be qualified as naive. Indeed, we have to address the fact that the distribution of the number of instances of each class is far from being uniform in our performance database. That is, we observe typically that one class contains the vast majority of the training examples for a problem. We argue that more suitable baseline for classification would be the results of a majority class classifier, i.e. a classifier which assigns to all instances the label

of the majoritarian class in the training data. In that case, the classification results presented in Section 4.5 are to be compared with the following values i.e. 65.92% for duration ratio, 62.62% for onset deviation, and 66.51% for energy variation. Concerning the performance event type prediction task, the classification baseline for this task is 92.29%.

4.4.2 Regression baseline

Expressive performance is a complex phenomenon and we believe the expressive deviations a performers introduces can not be considered as a linear combination of the score features. Linear regression is not the best choice to approximate non-linear functions. As confirmed by the results (Section 4.5), expressive performance does not seem to be a linear function on the attributes. Consequently, we have decided to include linear regression in our experiments as a baseline reference for the other methods.

4.5 Results

For modeling Task 1, we first present a comparative table for each of the expressive transformation aspects we are dealing with, namely note duration (Table 4.1), onset (Table 4.2) and energy (Table 4.3). In the case of Task 2, we present in Table 4.4 a comparison of the classification accuracy for all the classifiers listed above.

We performed a 10-fold cross validation for all the algorithms. In Table 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3, C.C.I refers to the correctly classified instances rate, C.C to the correlation coefficient, and R.A.E to the relative absolute error and R.R.S.E the root relative squared error which are calculated as follows. For the sake of clarity, we only indicate the C.C.I. in Table 4.4. Note that the formulas we present are used to compute statistics for each cross validation run. Consequently the values presented in Table 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4 are averaged over the 10 cross validation runs. This cross validation procedure can be seen as a first attempt to characterize the generalization accuracy of the induced models. However, we will discuss this approach in Section 4.7 and propose a harder generalization measurement in Chapter 6.

$$C.C.I = \frac{N_{C.C}}{N_{C.C} + N_{I.C}} \quad (4.1)$$

where $N_{C,C}$ (respectively $N_{I,C}$) stands for the total number of correctly (respectively incorrectly) classified instances.

$$C.C = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})(T_i - \bar{T})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (T_i - \bar{T})^2}} \quad (4.2)$$

$$R.A.E = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |O_i - T_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^N |T_i - \bar{T}|} \quad (4.3)$$

$$R.R.S.E = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - T_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (T_i - \bar{T})^2}} \quad (4.4)$$

In equations 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4, N is number of instances considered in a given cross validation run, O_i is the output value of the model for the example indexed by i , T_i is the target value for the example indexed by i , $\bar{O}$ (respectively $\bar{T}$) is the mean of the output (respectively target) for all the instances considered in the run.

The main indicators for the numerical algorithms and classification algorithms are the correlation coefficient and the correctly classified instances, respectively. The correlation coefficient measures the statistical correlation between the predicted and actual values. Note that here a higher number means a better model, with a 1 meaning perfect statistical correlation and a 0 meaning there is no correlation at all. This performance measure is only used for numerical input and output. The correctly classified instances rate is self-explanatory. Relative absolute error is the total absolute error made relative to what the error would have been if the prediction simply had been the average of the actual values. Root relative squared error is the total squared error made relative to what the error would have been if the prediction had been the average of the absolute value. This error exaggerates the cases in which the prediction error was significantly greater than the mean error.

Among the regression methods we explored, model tree regression is consistently the most accurate method. Among the classification methods we explored, Inductive Logic Programming is the most accurate classification

method. This can be explained by the fact that Inductive Logic Programming uses background knowledge for inducing the model. Thus, the algorithm allows to consider wider temporal windows (via the *succ* predicate), as opposed to the fixed width window containing only a note and its immediate neighbors. A positive result is that the requirement of inducing an understandable model does not involve any penalty in terms of accuracy (compared to the other classification methods).

4.5.1 Models are tempo-specific

A closer look at the best performing models reveals that all of them are markedly using the tempo deviation feature. The resulting Model Trees makes use of comparisons involving the tempo deviation feature in 65.3% (respectively 71.7%, and 62%) of the cases when predicting the duration ratio (respectively onset deviation, energy relative variation). 52.6% of the ILP model tests involve the tempo deviation feature. This may support the growing evidence that performance is tempo-specific Timmers and Honing [2002]; Honing [2006]; Grachten et al. [2006].

4.6 A performance rendering and explanation tool

Our ultimate aim lies in rendering expressive performances from nominal score melodies. We propose a method for integrating separate prediction models in order to render a performance, and then used this *aggregate of models* to build a performance rendering and explanation tool. This tool is intended to be a proof of concept of the presented approach.

4.6.1 Aggregating separate prediction models

To achieve this, we need to integrate the best models presented in previous section. So far we induced models for choosing the type of performance event to be applied (Task 2), and other models for characterizing a transformation event. Additionally, other secondary models need to be induced in order to characterize the modalities of ornamentation events, fragmentation events, and consolidation events, respectively. These tasks were not mentioned in

Algorithm	C.C.I(%)	C.C	R.A.E(%)	R.R.S.E(%)
C4.5	74.59	-	68.07	86.84
C4.5 with Boosting	72.99	-	72.87	87.35
Random Forest	70.51	-	62.74	89.85
KStar	73.71	-	63.04	86.65
KNN	67.15	-	72.77	95.57
Naive Bayes	59.97	-	98.18	103.07
ILP	80.37	-	45.25	76.96
Linear Regression	-	0.33	98.69	94.39
Least Med Square Regression	-	0.29	95.22	96.60
Model Tree Regression	-	0.72	74.89	69.14
SVM Regression (1)	-	0.29	95.30	96.15
SVM Regression (2)	-	0.48	89.01	88.24
SVM Regression (3)	-	0.66	76.65	75.47
SVM Regression (4)	-	0.70	81.11	71.23

Table 4.1: Cross validation results for duration ratio (Task 1)

Algorithm	C.C.I(%)	C.C	R.A.E(%)	R.R.S.E(%)
C4.5	78.61	-	68.47	88.12
C4.5 with Boosting	78.56	-	57.72	87.72
Random Forest	78.09	-	59.22	85.73
KStar	76.49	-	66.34	88.63
KNN	74.27	-	82.46	94.87
Naive Bayes	68.85	-	104.87	104.03
ILP	90.02	-	70.12	87.45
Linear Regression	-	0.17	101.12	98.41
Least Med Square Regression	-	0.01	92.50	101.32
Model Tree Regression	-	0.43	91.51	90.16
SVM Regression (1)	-	0.14	99.92	98.88
SVM Regression (2)	-	0.24	89.34	98.18
SVM Regression (3)	-	0.38	95.41	92.50
SVM Regression (4)	-	0.44	94.56	90.34

Table 4.2: Cross validation results for onset deviation (Task 1)

Algorithm	C.C.I(%)	C.C	R.A.E(%)	R.R.S.E(%)
C4.5	72.83	-	55.38	76.25
C4.5 with Boosting	73.3	-	44.56	74.1
Random Forest	70.3	-	51.7	78.04
KStar	70.92	-	52.42	75.5
KNN	58.01	-	61.91	102.67
Naive Bayes	54.8	-	80.17	91.16
ILP	79.8	-	36.61	71.52
Linear Regression	-	0.27	95.69	96.13
Least Med Square Regression	-	0.22	87.92	108.01
Model Tree Regression	-	0.67	66.31	74.31
SVM Regression (1)	-	0.25	89.28	98.57
SVM Regression (2)	-	0.47	82.53	89.4
SVM Regression (3)	-	0.56	75.47	82.95
SVM Regression (4)	-	0.64	69.28	77.23

Table 4.3: Cross validation results for energy variation (Task 1)

Algorithm	C.C.I(%)
C4.5	94.16
C4.5 with Boosting	94.06
Random Forest	93.82
KStar	96.14
KNN	93.50
Naive Bayes	89.47
ILP	96.18

Table 4.4: Cross validation results for the event type prediction (Task 2)

last section because the small amount of data available in the database for these performance events (see Section 3.2.2.2) makes irrelevant any attempt to measure the generalization power of the algorithms for these tasks. As a result, we aggregated these models using the following scheme:

```

INPUT: Nominal Score ns
OUTPUT: Rendered Performance rp
REPEAT for note in ns
  type = model-event-type(note)
  SWITCH type
    CASE transformation:
      Apply model-transformation(note)
    CASE ornamentation:
      Apply model-ornamentation(note)
    CASE consolidation:
      Apply model-consolidation(note)
    CASE: fragmentation
      Apply model-fragmentation(note)
  END
END

```

Here, model-event-type refers to the performance event type prediction model presented used for Task 2, model-transformation refers to the transformation event characterization model used in Task 1. Note this latter model is indeed an aggregate of three separate models for predicting duration ratio, onset deviation, and energy relative variation. Additionally, model-ornamentation, model-consolidation, and model-fragmentation are aggregates of models intended to characterize ornamentations, consolidations and fragmentations, respectively.

4.6.2 the ProGUI tool

The ProGUI tool [Ramirez and Hazan, 2006] was designed as a proof of concept to study the validity of our approach. It transforms an inexpressive melody input into an expressive one using the induced model and is able to explain the predictions it makes by presenting to the user relevant rules which capture expressive performance regularities. The tool is capable of

either generate an expressive MIDI performance from an inexpressive MIDI description of a melody and generate an expressive audio file from an inexpressive audio file. Figure 4.1 shows a snapshot of the system applied to a MIDI performance.

In addition to synthesizing an expressive performance of a piece, the tool may be able to provide explanations related to the transformations it has performed. Once a transformed note is selected requesting an explanation, the tool extracts the relevant rules generated by the classification model and present them to the user.

4.7 Summary and discussion

We described in this chapter how we applied data mining techniques for inducing models able to represent some aspects of expressive music performance (i.e. type of performance events, characteristics of the performance events) We used classification and regression techniques for modeling separately these aspects, and integrated the resulting models into an *aggregate of models*. Based on a 10-fold cross validation, we obtained the best regression results using Model Trees (in one case Support Vector Machine outperformed Model Trees). The best classification results were obtained using Inductive Logic Programming for all the modeling tasks we considered. The overall results might be improved by providing new features in order to represent the melodic feature space more accurately. Additionally, we are interested in increasing substantially the database size in order to provide more examples to the system. Based on this, we defined a scheme to apply these expressive transformation models on nominal scores within the ProGUI performance rendering tool.

However, from the opposite point of view, the presented approach might be considered as a fairly straightforward engineering solution to the problem, and we might point out the following issues:

- Separate models: One of the major drawback of this approach is that we have to build separate models for each of the expressive feature we have measure and we want to model. One strong assumption of this first approach is that the expressive feature we want to predict are independent. This leads to build separate models, which are therefore prone to provide inconsistent predictions. The close relationships that

The screenshot shows a software interface with two MIDI staves. The top staff is labeled 'Inexpressive' and the bottom staff is labeled 'Transformed'. Both staves show a sequence of notes and rests over a timeline with markers for measures 5, 6, 7, and 8. The 'Transformed' staff shows more complex rhythmic patterns and dynamics compared to the 'Inexpressive' staff.

An information window is open at the bottom, displaying the following explanation rules for the third note in the melody:

```

durratio_exp(A,B,C,same):-context(A,C,[nargroup(p,1)]).
onsetdev_exp(A,B,C,same).
energy_exp(A,B,C,same):-next_int(A,B,C,-3),prev_int(A,B,C,-3),prev_dur(A,B,C,1).
orna_exp(A,B,C,ornamentation):-succ(A,B,C,D),succ(A,B,D,E),succ(A,B,E,F),context(A,F,[nargroup(vp,3),nargroup(reverse_ip,2)]).
  
```

The window also features a blue information icon on the left and an 'OK' button on the right.

Figure 4.1: Expressive performance generator tool showing the inexpressive MIDI description of a fragment of *Body and Soul* and the transformed expressive MIDI description together with the explanation rules for the third note in the melody

exist between different expressive aspects (e.g. duration ratio and onset deviation or onset deviation and ornamentation event) are ignored.

- Scalability: In the presented approach, we deal with a very subset of what has been described as expressivity in Section 1.2. We would like to make our approach general for addressing other expressive aspects in the future. However, the approach we presented in this chapter may already be seen as rather complex *montage* because it involves nesting several models for each considered characteristic. We argue that this approach is hardly scalable for future applications. It is true that some algorithms contain multi-variate prediction mechanism (e.g. vector regression is implemented in Blockeel and Raedt [1998]), which would allow to produce more compact models and would consequently reduce the complexity of the model aggregate. Nevertheless, we believe our approach requires a multi-goal approach for addressing the wide range of expressive transformations.
- Lack of control: Finally, we want to stress that if we can optimize each model by modifying its specific parameters and choosing the database it will be trained with, these parameters are not related to any perceptual aspect of the performance. We also illustrate this issue by taking the example of the 10-fold cross validation scheme used in this chapter. Indeed, the database is split on a vector basis and the structure of the database, namely a set performances related to a set of scores, is lost. As a consequence, meaningless train/test splits are likely to occur. For instance, the performance events related to the first and third note of a given excerpt can be included in the training set while the performance events related to the second note are included in the test set, which leads to erroneous generalization measurements. Overall, the approach presented in this chapter lacks of mechanisms for controlling and constraining the induction of models in a meaningful way.

Based on these ideas, we would like to consider some alternatives to the approach presented in this chapter. We present in next chapter an approach based on Evolutionary Computation (EC), called Evolutionary Population of Generative Models (EPGM).

Chapter 5

Evolutionary Population of Generative Models

We present in this chapter a novel approach called Evolutionary Population of Generative Models (EPGM). The EPGM key ideas can be summarized as follows:

- **Evolutionary:** The basic framework in which EPGM is built is evolutionary computation. By analogy with nature, a population of solution is evolved and the fittest individuals survive.
- **Population:** Here, each individual of the population is an autonomous model. This contrasts with approaches in which the whole population forms a model and provides several alternative solutions at the end of the evolutionary process.
- **Generative:** Each model is intended to provide predictions of any data type (labels, numbers, arbitrary data structures). A prediction generator is involved in the evolutionary process.
- **Model:** EPGM evolves models in to order to fit and generalize a set of observed data.

Here, we aim to build expressive performance models based on evolutionary computation, and develop a specific instance of the general approach using the Strongly Typed Genetic Programming Paradigm. We will first introduce the evolutionary computation field, previous evolutionary approaches

for addressing learning and musical problems, and the arguments that led us to concentrate our research in this direction. Then, we will develop a detailed overview of the EPGM approach.

5.1 Why use Evolutionary Computation?

5.1.1 A brief introduction to EC techniques

We present in this section an overview of some techniques used in the EC field. The first two, namely Genetic Algorithms and Genetic Programming, are commonly used by EC researchers nowadays, while the third one is an extension of Genetic Programming that we will show is of particular interest for the EPGM architecture.

5.1.1.1 Genetic Algorithms

Genetic Algorithms (GA) can be seen as a general optimization method that searches a large space of candidate hypotheses seeking one that perform best according to a fitness function. As presented by Holland [1975], GA transform a population of individuals, each with an associated value of fitness (i.e. ability to solve the problem), into a new generation of the population. The new generation is obtained using the Darwinian principles of survival and reproduction of the fittest and analogs of naturally occurring genetic operations such as crossover and mutation.

5.1.1.2 Genetic Programming

Koza [1992] presents the Genetic Programming (GP) extension. While in the GA framework individuals are typically represented as binary or float strings, in the GP paradigm the structures undergoing adaptation are hierarchical computer programs of dynamically varying size and structure. These computer programs are represented as trees, in which a node represents a function, while each leaf is a terminal (e.g. input of the computer program). Since its inception more than fifteen years ago, GP has been successfully used to solve practical problems.

5.1.1.3 Strongly Typed Genetic Programming

According to Montana [1993], in standard GP, there is no way to restrict the programs it generates to those where the functions operate on appropriate data types. When the programs manipulate multiple data types and contain functions designed to operate on particular data types, this can lead to unnecessarily large search times and/or unnecessarily poor generalization performance. Montana presented an enhanced version of GP called Strongly Typed Genetic Programming (STGP) which enforces data type constraints. Using this approach, it is possible to specify what type of data a given GP primitive can accept as argument (e.g. type of input), or can return (e.g. output).

5.1.2 Evolutionary Computation and learning

Koza [1992] shows that Evolutionary Computation has been successfully applied to concept learning and empirical discovery tasks. In particular, concept formation using GP is addressed in [Koza, 1991; De Jong et al., 1993]. These approach are extended by Divina and Marchiori [2002] and Thie and Giraud-Carrier [2005], in which higher-order representations can be used. Zhang and Smart [2006] introduce a class probability prediction derived from gaussian distribution in GP from classification tasks such as face recognition. Overall, evolutionary strategies provide good exploration capabilities compared with traditional hill-climbing search methods, however these works also highlight the necessity of incorporating specific mechanisms for restricting the search space to useful solutions. Also EC and GP turned out to be accurate for solving symbolic regression problems, e.g. fitting data from a sampled polynomial function, see [Koza, 1992]. There is growing evidence that EC is a competitive paradigm for addressing concept learning, nevertheless few works have focussed on inductive systems which are able to provide numerical predictions.

5.1.3 Evolutionary Computation and music

Evolutionary computation has been considered with growing interest in musical applications as pointed out by Miranda [2004]. A large number of experimental systems using evolutionary techniques to generate musical compositions have been proposed, including Cellular Automata Music [Millen,

Figure 5.1: A typical Genetic Algorithm setting applied to music

1990], a Cellular Automata Music Workstation [Hunt et al., 1991], CAMUS [Miranda, 1993], GenDash [Waschka II, 1999], CAMUS 3D [McAlpine et al., 1999], Vox Populi [Manzoli et al., 1999], Synthetic Harmonies [Bilotta et al., 2000], Living Melodies [Dahlstedt and Nordhal, 2001] and Genophone [Mandelis, 2003]. Composition systems based on genetic algorithms generally follow the standard genetic algorithm approach for evolving musical materials such as melodies, rhythms and chords. We summarize this approach in Figure 5.1. In these systems, the fitness function is based on several criteria: melodic fitness, harmonic fitness and voice range fitness. On other systems, the fitness is driven by interactive evaluation (i.e. human evaluation), or by a separate *critic* subsystem. Evolutionary computation has also been considered for improvisation applications such as [Biles, 1994], where a genetic algorithm-based model of a novice Jazz musician learning to improvise was developed. The system evolves a set of melodic ideas that are mapped into notes considering the chord progression being played. Here, the fitness function is also altered by the feedback of the human playing with the system.

Nevertheless, very few works focusing on the use of evolutionary computation for expressive performance modeling have been done. To the best of our knowledge, the only work in this direction is the work by Grachten et al. [2004] where the weights of the edit-distance operations are optimized

by a genetic algorithm in order to annotate a human Jazz performance. In contrast, we suggest here that Evolutionary Computation may be considered as a central aspect of the modeling approach we investigate. We argue that if EC can address both concept learning, and musical tasks in a unified framework, that is, the evolution of populations of solutions, this technique has a great potential for modeling expressive performance which combines both of these aspects.

In next section, we will first introduce some particular features of evolutionary computation that make this technique more flexible and scalable than most of the standard data mining techniques presented in Chapter 4.

5.2 System overview

The central idea of EPGM is to evolve a population of performance models. Each model should be able to generate precise predictions by generalizing subsets of the performance database presented in Chapter 3. Basically, each individual in the population can be seen as a regression tree. However, as we will see below, the predictions returned by a model do not necessarily need to be nominal labels (as in e.g. classification) or numbers (as in e.g. regression). Also, it is important to note here that the models are the results of the evolutionary process rather than being induced in a greedy top-down fashion.

We first propose some specific arguments in favor of EC, and more specifically STGP as the central framework of the system. Then, we will introduce the EPGM in details by presenting the types, primitives, terminals, genetic operators which are used. We will then present some fitness measurements for addressing specific musical tasks. Finally, in the next chapter, the results of preliminary modeling experiments will be presented.

5.2.1 Aims

We have seen in Chapter 4 that expressive music performance is hard to model from a computational point of view. This is partly due to the facts that we deal with an inexact phenomenon and that it is not straightforward to formalize either melodic context, performance events or model accuracy measures. We propose to develop a learning strategy which will emphasize the following ideas.

5.2.1.1 Population of performance models

Human Performance is an inexact phenomenon: a musician could hardly reproduce identically a given performance. This is particularly true in jazz music, where the improvisational contribution to a performance is fundamental. At each new rendition, small alterations in the timing and other expressive features of the musical piece are introduced. Expressive performance models should take into account this aspect. In contrast, traditional decision tree such as C4.5 [Quinlan, 1993] are essentially deterministic. That is, once induced, a feature-based decision tree model will produce a constant sequence of predictions for transforming a fragment presenting a constant melodic sequence. EC provide an elegant way to cope with this limitation by evolving a population of models, with benefits for both end-users and researchers. First, the result of an evolution is a population of transformation models that will eventually produce different musical transformations. Moreover, each model is *ranked* according to its fitness. The end-user can merely choose to keep the best-ranked model transformation. Alternatively he has the opportunity to navigate through the whole population and select the transformation of other models on an aesthetic basis. Conversely, by analyzing the whole population of models, and especially the best and least-ranked models, the researcher has to opportunity to appreciate on several examples the results of specific design decisions and to refine the fitness function.

5.2.1.2 Custom data types for structured modeling and prediction

Although it is possible to use evolutionary computation techniques in a straightforward way i.e. using templates and well-defined data types, the EC programmer is free to design custom data types for the model inputs and outputs. In the case of STGP, it is possible to refine the input/output specifications for each primitive of the genetic program. Here, we make use of such flexibility to define a structured prediction data type that takes into account features of note timing, ornamentations, consolidations. This is a first step towards a more complete prediction of performance events. We will present this prediction type in details in next section.

5.2.1.3 Integration of domain-specific knowledge

When modeling a given problem, it can be decisive to integrate elements of domain-specific knowledge in the system in order to reduce effectively the

search space. In the case of feature-based tree modelling, one can define this knowledge at several levels. First, the tree structure has to be defined so that it matches a regression tree structure. Also, one can easily handle the prior distribution of inputs and outputs by defining the initialization operator for each primitive in use in the genetic program. In our case, we refer to *constant generation*: on the one hand, features are compared to constants across the successive tests, these constants have to respect the statistical distribution of the feature space. This allows to restrict the search space to potentially accurate solutions. On the other hand, single or even structured constant predictions are generated independently to where they will appear in a tree. Consequently, the role of the initialization operator is to provide a first guess for both features and prediction values. Finally, the most powerful aspect of evolutionary techniques is that the user has the freedom (and the responsibility) to define a fitness function that is suitable for a given problem. This makes possible to include elaborate accuracy measurements such as performance similarity in the evolution process.

We will then present a modeling strategy based on Strongly Typed Genetic Programming. We will see how the ideas presented above can be integrated in this framework.

5.2.2 Using STGP for building regression trees

Montana STGP extension is of interest in the context of building a Regression Tree model for expressive music performance. Indeed, tests operate on input variables of the program, that is, inputs are compared to inputs which appear in the training set. On the other hand, leaves of the trees contain predictions which should reflect the distribution of outputs in the training set. It is possible to use STGP types to implement these *structural constraints* in the evolutionary process. Firstly, the types and primitives of the system are presented.

5.2.3 Types and primitives

The **IF** primitive tests whether its first argument of type *Bool* is true or false. If the test succeeds, its second argument is returned, otherwise its third argument is returned (both second and third arguments have a *RegValue* type). The **LT** primitive tests whether its first argument is lower than the second argument (The former has a *InputValue* type and the latter *FeatValue*). The

Primitive Name	Nb. args.	Arg. Type	Return Type
IF	3	1st: <i>Bool</i> , 2nd and 3rd: <i>RegValue</i>	<i>RegValue</i>
LT	2	1st: <i>InputValue</i> , 2nd <i>FeatValue</i>	<i>Bool</i>
EFeatValue	0	-	<i>FeatValue</i>
ERegValue	0	-	<i>RegValue</i>

Table 5.1: STGP primitives used in this study. Each primitive is presented along with the number of arguments it handles, the type of each argument, and its return type. Note that primitives **EFeatValue** and **ERegValue**, which are used for constant generation, take no argument as input.

primitive returns a *Bool* which value is true if the test succeeds, false otherwise. Given the definitions of our types, we can see that during the building process the output of the **LT** primitive will always be connected to the first argument of the **IF** primitive. Instead, we could have chosen to use a single primitive **IFLT** with 4 arguments (the first two being involved in *InputValue* typed comparison, and the last two being used to return a *RegValue*). However, we think that restricting the tests to inequalities would be a constraint for future developments. **EFeatValue** and **ERegValue** are zero-argument primitives. We use them for generating constants. The first one generates constants to be involved in inequality tests (primitive **LT**).

5.2.4 Logical consistency and code bloat

Is type consistency a sufficient condition for obtaining useful models? We can illustrate this question with the example shown in Figure 5.2 two prototypical models that are type consistent. Both models perform 2 successive tests involving the *InputValue* primitive labelled **IN0**. The root of both trees, indicated by an arrow, first tests whether **IN0** is lower than a constant equal to 0. If the test succeeds, an ERV primitive connected to the second argument of the root is returned. Otherwise, a new test is performed via the right-most **IF** primitive, checking whether **IN0** is either lower than 1 (upper model), or -1 (lower model). We can see that the upper model is logically consistent: its tests are plausibly structured and can possibly represent the feature space.

Oppositely, the lower model is logically inconsistent: because the right-most test is not logically consistent with the left-most one, all the primitives marked in gray turn to be useless. This leads to a situation of *code bloat* Tackett [1995] where the evolved tree may contain useless branches, called

Figure 5.2: Two type-consistent regression trees. (Top) Logically consistent tree, (Bottom) Logically inconsistent tree. Typed connections between primitives are appearing. Also, constants generated by zero-arguments primitives appear in parentheses. EFV stands for EFeatValue, while ERV stands for ERegValue. The arrow indicates the output point of the program.

introns. The influence of code bloat in the results of an evolutionary system is still debated and may depend of the model application domain. However, in this work, because our work is preliminary, we decided to discard individuals containing such introns by introducing a logical consistency check mechanism. As a future extension, we plan to study thoroughly the influence of such introns in the evolutionary process for our particular domain.

5.2.5 Terminals

Constants have to be generated by the evolutionary system at two levels. Firstly, the score context inputs serve as terminals (e.g. `IN0` in Figure 5.2). These inputs are compared with constants during the successive tests. On the other hand, constants have to be generated for producing numerical predictions. `ERV` and `EFV` initialization operators are used to integrate the distribution of the both inputs and outputs in the training data.

5.2.5.1 Implementing arbitrary prediction types: the `ERegValue` primitive

As mentioned earlier, a key feature of EPGM is its flexibility regarding the data types it predicts. This has to be compared with the rather rigid classification/regression framework in which most machine learning techniques are defined. In EPGM, the outcome of an `IF` primitive is *RegValue*-typed. We have created different instances of the `ERegValue` primitive to address different modeling tasks. These instances are the following.

- **Scalar**: This is the simplest setting, in which the `ERV` primitive contains a float. In this case, the evolved models are regression trees. We use this setting in preliminary experiments in order to predict the duration ratio, see Section 6.1.2. In the rest of this document, we will refer to this setting as **ERegValue-1**
- **Array of scalars**: In this case the EPGM evolves multivariate regression trees which predict vectors. We use this setting in order to predict the characteristics of a transformation event. Therefore, a three-dimensional array of floats is used in order to predict the triplet [duration ratio, onset deviation, energy relative variation]. We use this setting in the experiment described in Section 6.1.3. This setting will be referred to as **ERegValue-2**.

Member Name	Type
Duration Ratio	float
Onset Deviation	float
Relative Loudness	float
Ornamentation Event	bool
Ornamentation Relative Onset	float
Ornamentation Absolute Duration	float
Ornamentation Relative Pitch	float
Ornamentation Relative Loudness	float
Consolidation Event	bool
Consolidation Relative Duration	float

Table 5.2: Members of the **ERegValue-3** primitive

- Data structure: We finally increase the complexity of the **ERegValue** data type in order to predict a wider range of performance events. We present the resulting primitive **ERegValue-3**. Its members are presented in table 5.2.

Following we explain how we aim to use this data type for generating performance events. The first three **ERegValue-3** members, namely Duration Ratio, Onset Deviation and Relative Loudness, are float-valued and they refer to a transformation event. The fourth member, namely Ornamentation Event, is a boolean value indicating whether an ornamentation will be generated. If it is false, no ornamentation will be generated, and members 5 to 8 (namely Ornamentation Relative Onset, Ornamentation Absolute Duration, Ornamentation Relative Pitch and Ornamentation Relative Loudness) are ignored. Otherwise, we use these float-valued members to generate the ornamentation. The ninth **ERegValue** member, namely Consolidation Event, is a boolean indicating whether a consolidation will be generated. Otherwise, the last Consolidation Relative Duration member is used along with the three first members to produce a consolidation. Note that this design allow the system to predict the following combinations of events: transformation, ornamentation+transformation, consolidation, ornamentation+consolidation (see Section 1.4.2 for a taxonomy of possible performance events).

Figure 5.3: Distribution of (a) duration ratio, (b) onset deviation, and (c) relative energy variation in the training data

5.2.5.2 Constant generation

Corresponding to each **ERegValue** instance, we create an initialization operator which initializes randomly the **ERegValue** members. We generate each member randomly according to its statistical distribution in the training data. As an example, we show in Figure 5.3 an the distribution of the three characteristics of a transformation events, namely duration ratio, onset deviation, and energy relative variation.

We approximate the distribution of each characteristic with a gaussian, and use the resulting gaussians to generate randomly members of the **ERegValue** primitive. This is a first step towards using a larger repertoire of possible statistical distributions. Overall, the constant generation step can be seen as a way of incorporating prior knowledge concerning the distribution of the score context and the performance events.

5.2.6 Genetic operators

The genetic operators we use are basically a refinement of the operators proposed by Koza [1992], and Montana [1993] in their Strongly Typed variant,

where the operation is constrained to produce a type-consistent structure. Operators are Tree Crossover, where two individuals can swap subtrees, and Standard Mutation, where a subtree is replaced by a newly generated one. Additionally, Shrink mutation replaces a branch with one of its child nodes, and Swap mutation swaps two subtrees of an individual. Also, two mutation operators were added to process the randomly-generated constants returned by `EFeatValue` and `ERegValue` primitives.

5.3 Fitness evaluation: characterizing the best individuals

The fitness evaluation component is one of the most important aspects of the evolutionary presented in this chapter. Apart from the structural constraints (implemented using types and primitives) and the genetic operators presented above, the fitness measurement is responsible of characterizing how accurate is a model in the population. This decision is important because individuals with a good fitness are likely to be selected for creating offsprings via crossover or mutation. These offsprings will be present in the next generation, while individuals with a bad ranking will tend to disappear from the population. Having in mind that the purpose of the EPGM is to evolve models that may fit and generalize the training database, we will present different strategies for measuring the training accuracy by comparing a model's outputs with the training data. This will answer the question of how similar the model behaves compared with the performer. This forms the supervised component of the fitness. But prior to this, we present an unsupervised component for ensuring that the input space will be represented in the most complete way.

5.3.1 Promoting a complete input space representation

We first describe a mechanism for promoting an accurate and balanced representation of the input space in the context of generative models. As pointed out in Gagné et al. [2006], pure error-driven fitness measurements in GP may lead to overfitting. Several papers have introduced the notion of *parsimony pressure* as a way to reduce the complexity of the models while improving the

generalization performances. This is relevant in the case of e.g. binary classification problems, however in some situations (we believe our application domain is one of these) a bias toward low-complexity does not improve the generalization performance of the model (Cavaretta and Chellapilla [1999]).

In our particular case, where the expressive transformations of musical excerpts result in delicate modifications in the timing, the simplest models would essentially let the score timing unaffected (see Section 4.4). Here, what we are interested in is a model that does not collapse rather dissimilar input vectors into the same leaf. In our case, this would mean that notes in very different contexts would be transformed equally.

We take an alternative approach, promoting a more complete representation of the input space. That is, different input vectors should produce different predictions, even if the corresponding predictions produce similar results. Thus, we enforce the model to reach as much leaves as possible when processing the set of input vectors of a fragment. We argue that this constraint provides a way of keeping the tree model balanced by giving in increased weight to the input space representation. We are aware that this criterion might affect the compactness of the tree model, however one has to consider this structural measure used in combination with the error-driven measure presented below.

To achieve this, we define a balance coefficient c_{bal} :

$$c_{bal} = \frac{n_{dpr}}{n_{di}} \tag{5.1}$$

where n_{dpr} is the number of distinct prediction leaves that were reached as a consequence of successive tests, and n_{di} is the total number of inputs vectors that differ in at least one feature.

5.3.2 Supervised accuracy measurement

We are ultimately interested in is how accurately a given model can learn to generate expressive fragments based on the performer database. This accuracy measurement provides a supervised constraint to the fitness function. We define two kinds of error assessments from different perspectives as explained below.

First one can measure the model accuracy by comparing, for a given training fragment, the actual performance events with the predicted performance events and obtain a transformation-based error. This approach is shown

Figure 5.4: Transformation-based error framework

in Figure 5.4, which is essentially what was considered in the approaches presented in 4.

From a slightly different perspective, we could measure how similar is a transformed melody with the actually performed fragment, which would result in a similarity-based error. In that case, there is no direct comparison between the actual set of transformations and the predictions returned by the model. This is a highly seductive approach, because in that case we do not directly focus on the details of the transformations. That is, no direct comparison is made between the actual set of transformations and the transformations predicted the model. This makes this measure very general and suitable for a broader range of melody high-level transformation problems (e.g. mood or style). We will return to this point in Chapter 7. We present this approach in Figure 5.5.

5.3.2.1 Transformation-based error

We define a fragment transformation error as the geometric mean of duration ratio, onset deviation, and energy variation mean relative errors over the training fragment. We call the average of this latter error over all the training fragments Global Relative Error (GRE).

First, we compute the error-driven fitness function by applying the following formula:

$$f_{error} = \frac{1}{1 + GRE} \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 5.5: Similarity-based framework

5.3.2.2 Melodic similarity measurement

To achieve this, we use a edit-distance that was fit to human performance similarity judgments, as proposed by Grachten et al. [2004]. For details about the edit-distance, we refer to the Section 3.2.2.1 in which the core computation as well as the edit-operations for melodic sequences are presented in order to compute an alignment between a performance melody and its corresponding nominal melody. Here, we use the same framework to compare two performance melodies. This is made possible by optimizing the edit-distance costs so that the resulting distance fits human performance similarity judgments, as shown below.

5.3.2.3 Fitting the distance to human performance similarity judgments

The cost parameters presented above were optimized in Grachten et al. [2006] to fit human performance similarity judgements based on a web survey ¹. In this survey, 92 subjects were presented a target performance A (the nominal performance, without expressive deviations) of a short musical fragment, and two different performances B and C of the same score fragment. The task was to indicate which of the two alternative performances was perceived as most similar to the target performance. The edit-distance cost parameters were optimized using a genetic algorithm to fit the survey results. We show in table 5.3 the final parameters values.

¹The survey is available on line at: <http://musje.iiia.csic.es/survey/introduction.html>

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α_1	α_2	α_3	β_1	β_2	β_3	π	δ	o	ϵ
0.031	0.875	0.243	0.040	0.330	0.380	0.452	1.000	0.120	0.545

Table 5.3: Optimized values of edit-operation cost parameters

The resulting melodic similarity measurement yielded to the best accuracy at the MIREX melodic similarity contest in 2005 [Grachten et al., 2005].

The optimized edit-distance is squashed because we use by convention a low (respectively high) fitness value for models that exhibit a high (respectively low) error. We obtain the final error-driven component value by applying the following formula:

$$f_{similarity} = \frac{1}{1 + editdistance} \quad (5.3)$$

5.3.3 Picking the best individuals: the *Hall of Fame*

The notion of *Hall of Fame* is useful in Evolutionary Computation. Indeed, as various individuals are generated at each generation, it is useful to keep an history of the best performing individuals so far. The usual procedure consists in storing the individuals which exhibit the best fitness measure in a separate buffer of fixed size. Here, our approach is oriented to model induction from empirical data, consequently the best-ranked models have to be seen as the models which exhibit the best *training* accuracy. Here we extend this mechanism by sorting the elements of the Hall of Fame according to their *generalization* accuracy. To achieve this, we proceed as follows: at each generation, the models present in the Hall of Fame are tested on a separate set of data. As an outcome, we obtain a new ranking of the Hall of Fame. In this new configuration, the best ranked model is the model which exhibits the best generalization accuracy among the Hall of Fame, i.e. the set of models which fit best the training data. As a result, we call best-so-far model the best ranked model of the Hall of Fame.

5.4 Summary

We reported in details the EPGM framework by presenting the typing constraints, primitives, constant generation mechanisms, genetic operators and fitness functions. In next chapter we will validate our approach by applying EPGM to several learning experiments, ranging from “toy” examples to full-scale situations. We will also study the impact of different design decisions and evolutionary parameters.

Chapter 6

Validation

We present in this chapter a preliminary set of experiments using EPGM to learn different musical tasks, namely single regression, transformation events characterization, and melody transformation. In that sense, this chapter has to be seen as the practical counterpart to the theoretical framework presented in previous chapter. We want to assess whether the approach can be applied to solve performance model induction tasks. If so, we are interested in studying the impact of specific decisions regarding our approach, such as the choice of the fitness function and its components, or the size of the evolved population. While the first experiments we present here are using a relatively small subset of the database presented in Chapter 3, we also use the whole database in latter experiments. We are interested in studying both learning and generalization accuracy of the EPGM approach, consequently we define a method for measuring both accuracies. We then present a discussion of the achieved results. This will lead us to the conclusions we will present in next chapter.

6.1 Experiments with EPGM

Before presenting the experiments, we give some details concerning the evolutionary settings we used along with details of implementation.

6.1.1 Evolutionary settings and implementation

We first present the evolutionary settings we use in the following experiments. We use a generational replacement algorithm with a tournament selection (the tournament size is equal to 5). Crossover probability is set to 0.9, with a branch-crossover probability of 0.2, which means that crossovers are more likely to be performed on leaves, with the effect of redistributing the constants and terminals in the tree. The Standard mutation probability is set to 0.01, while the Swap mutation has been set to a higher value (0.1) in order to let a individual reorganize its feature space partition with more probability. Finally, Shrink mutation probability is set 0.05. The maximum tree depth has been set to 20, which could lead to the generation of very complex individuals. The size of the population is changed from one experiment to another one. For small-scale experiments we can use a population size of 200 individuals, while we will see a population size of 1000 individuals is needed for inducing successfully the performance models in larger-scale experiments. We stop the evolution if the fitness reaches a value of 0.95 (in all cases the maximum possible fitness is 1). Additionally, we use a convergence stopping criterion, i.e. we stop the evolution if there is no significant improvement of the best individual fitness. Note that, in some cases, we will summarize the evolution of the models to a limited number of generations for the sake of clarity.

We have implemented the whole EPGM system within the Open Beagle Framework [Gagné and Parizeau, 2005]. Open Beagle is a C++ object oriented framework for Evolutionary Computation. While Open Beagle was primarily designed for solving Genetic Programming tasks, it now supports other Evolutionary Computation techniques such as Genetic Algorithms, or Coevolution. We believe it is a flexible platform for implementing the EPGM component and will allow a range of future extension to our approach. Furthermore, we definitely need to use an efficient framework due to the amount of computation we perform in Evolutionary Computation. All the experiments were carried with a Debian 1.6 GHz Centrino computer with a memory of 512 Mb.

6.1.2 Experiment 1: Prediction of the duration ratio

In this first experiment, presented in Hazan et al. [2006], we use EPGM in order the build a predict the duration ratio of transformation events. Consequently, this task can be seen as a unidimensional regression problem;

therefore we can directly compare the behavior of the system with the best-performing approach presented in Chapter 4. We included in this experiment a small subset of the whole database, namely 2 versions of *Body and Soul* played around the nominal tempo (e.g. 60 and 65 beats per minute) and 2 versions of *Like Someone In Love* also played around the nominal tempo (e.g. 120 and 140 beats per minute). We used a population size of 200 individuals along with the settings presented above. The evolutionary run presented here was completed in approximately 2 hours.

In Figure 6.1, we present the RMSE of the best-so-far model when predicting the note duration ratio of the four excerpts presented above. On the top, the model is only trained with one of the four fragments, namely *Body and Soul* played at 60 beats per minute, i.e. the fitness function is only based on this error. On the bottom, the model is trained using the four fragments. First we can see that excerpts that share the same melodic representation evolve in a similar fashion. In the case of being trained with only one song (top of Figure 6.1), the prediction error start to differentiate at generation 200. After this point, predictions concerning the training and similar fragments (i.e. with the same melodic context) become better while predictions concerning dissimilar fragments become worse. On the other hand (bottom of Figure 6.1), when all the fragments are used during training, the error tends to be minimized for the four excerpts. Figure. 6.2 shows the note by note Squared Error of the duration ratio during the evolution process. First generation model error appear on the back while last generation model error is on the front. We can see, that even if the overall error is minimized, some notes, such as note 61, 80, and 85 are modelled with less accuracy. This means that the best tree model does not cover these melodic situations appropriately.

Finally, in Figure 6.3, we perform an informal comparison between two models and the training data when predicting the duration ratio of each note from the test excerpt *Like Someone In Love* played at 140 beats per minute. The first model is the best-so-far STGP model obtained for this task (indicated in grey dotted line). The second model (grey dashed line) was obtained using a Model Tree algorithm, which proved to be the best-performing algorithm for this task in the comparison we present in Chapter 4. The black solid line corresponds to the actual training data for this excerpt. We can see that both EPGM and Model Trees behave qualitatively well, nevertheless a thorough comparison has to be completed in order to compare quantitatively both approaches on the same database.

Figure 6.1: Experiment 1. Best-so-far individual RMSE for each of the target songs when the fitness takes into account only the *Body And Soul* (played at 60 beats per minute) prediction error (top), or when the fitness takes into account prediction the error of the four fragments (bottom). Gray solid (respectively dashed) line is the RMSE of *Body And Soul* played at 60 (respectively 65) beats per minute. Black solid (respectively dashed) line is the RMSE of *Like Someone In Love* played at 120 (respectively 140) beats per minute.

6.1.3 Experiment 2: Characterization of transformation events

In this second experiment, initially presented in Hazan and Ramirez [2006] we evolve models which can predict transformation-events (i.e. a triplet [duration ratio, onset deviation, energy variation]). Therefore, we use in this experiment the **ERegValue-2** primitive along with its random generator. We compare two fitness functions for this problem.

Figure 6.2: Experiment 1. Note by note squared error of the duration ratio during the evolution process

Figure 6.3: Experiment 1. Note by note duration ratio prediction for *Like Someone in Love* played at 140 beats per minute. Black solid line refers to the performance training data, grey dotted line refers to the best-so-far STGP model, and grey dashed line corresponds to a Model Tree as presented in Chapter 4

- Fitness 1: This is an error-driven fitness function f_{error} as defined in Section 5.3.2.1.
- Fitness 2: This is a hybrid fitness function that integrates both error-driven and the unsupervised component promoting a complete representation of the input space. We obtain it by computing the geometric mean between c_{bal} averaged over the training fragments and f_{error} .

6.1.3.1 *One fragment out* cross validation

The first experiment presented above has been the starting point of our research, nevertheless the little amount of data is probably insufficient for us to characterize the robustness of the system when processing a greater amount of training data. Furthermore, it is not statistically meaningful to evaluate the accuracy of the system based on a unique and arbitrary split of the database into train and test data. Consequently, we need to define a cross-validation scheme which respects the nature of the data. We present a *One fragment out* cross validation scheme for evaluating both training and test accuracy of the system. Indeed, all the excerpts we have stored in the database are composed of several fragments (between two and four). At the beginning of an EPGM run, we randomly pick a fragment of each excerpt in the database: this fragment will be used as test data. The rest of the data is considered as training material. Proceeding this way, we ensure that excerpts that share the same melodic material are not used in both training and test set. This makes this cross validation a *hard* validation scheme compared to standard approaches in which the database is split on a vector basis, as a consequence the same melodic material may be present in training and test set. Consequently, we use the *One fragment out* cross validation scheme in the following experiment by running each trial five times. The results appearing below are averaged over these five trials.

6.1.3.2 Results

We present the results of five cross validation runs as presented above. We first perform a cross validation run on a small subset of the database containing four excerpts played at nominal tempo, namely *Body And soul*, *Once I loved*, *Up Jumped Spring* and *Like Someone In Love*. For this small dataset, the whole cross validation run was completed in approximately 4 hours.

Figure 6.4 shows the Global Relative Error measurements of the best-so-far tree model during the evolution. The legend of the figure is the following: Plain (respectively dashed) grey plot corresponds to the results of the best-so-far model evolved with the fitness 1 and tested on the training (respectively test) cases. Plain (respectively dotted) black plot corresponds to the results of the best-so-far model evolved with fitness 2 and tested on the training (respectively test) cases. First, we can notice an overall decrease of the GRE measured on the training data for both fitness measures. This shows that, for both fitness measures, the system is able to evolve models that minimize the error on the training data. We also notice that the models evolved with fitness 2 exhibit an error that spans a considerably larger range than the error measured on models evolved with fitness 1. Fitness 2 best-so-far model error turns to be the smallest after 70 generations, which shows that the hybrid fitness function produces a better fit on the training data. Secondly, we focus on the test error exhibited by the best-so-far models evolved with both fitness measurements. For both families of models, we identify an overfitting point in which the test error gets larger than the training error, this point is reached later in the case of models evolved with Fitness 2 (generation 45) than with models evolved with fitness 1 (generation 20). Overall, it seems that models evolved with Fitness 1 do not provide the best training accuracy while exhibiting the best generalization capabilities, while models evolved based on Fitness 2 show a better learning accuracy and are less accurate in generalizing.

We reproduce these findings based on a larger scale experiment. Here, we consider all the transformation events in the database presented in Chapter 3, namely 3848 transformation events. The whole cross validation run required more than 60 hours to be completed. We present the results of this large scale validation as following. Figure 6.5 compares the training accuracy, Figure 6.6 compares the test accuracy, and Figure 6.7 compares the model size for the two fitness settings presented above. These results confirm that Fitness 1 yields better generalization accuracy, while Fitness 2 promotes the training accuracy. Furthermore we can see in Figure 6.7 that the hybrid fitness function “grows” the models much faster than the error-driven fitness function, even if the resulting models exhibit a smaller generalization accuracy. Conversely, the error driven fitness function ends up with models that provide a best generalization accuracy at the price of a slow evolution.

Figure 6.4: Experiment 2. Global Relative Error of the best-so-far model during the evolution in four settings (Small data set, averaged on five cross validation runs). Plain grey: fitness 1, training data. Dashed grey: fitness 1, test data. Plain black: fitness 2, training data. Dotted black : fitness 2, test data.

6.1.4 Experiment 3: Prediction of a wider range of performance events

We finally present the last experiment involving the prediction of a wider range of performance events, as presented in Section 5.2.5.1. Consequently we make use of the **ERegValue-3** prediction type along with its corresponding random generator. Corresponding to each score note, the **ERegValue-3** data type enables to model the following combinations of performance events: transformation, ornamentation+transformation, consolidation, ornamentation+consolidation. The fitness evaluation is achieved using the melodic similarity driven fitness function presented in Section 5.3.2.2. We present a preliminary run achieved on a subset of the database, namely the small subset presented in previous section. Note that we were not able to achieve a cross validation run for this experiment due to the massive use of computer resources needed to achieve a single run (the presented run was completed in approximately 18h).

Figure 6.8 shows a plot of the average edit-distance over the training frag-

Figure 6.5: Experiment 2. Training Global Relative Error of the best-so-far model during the evolution (Whole data set, averaged on five cross validation runs). Dotted: Fitness 1, Plain: Fitness 2

Figure 6.6: Experiment 2. Test Global Relative Error of the best-so-far model during the evolution (Whole data set, averaged on five cross validation runs). Dotted: Fitness 1, Plain: Fitness 2

ments (solid) and the test fragments (dashed) for the best-of-run model during the evolution. We can notice a first period in which the overall distance to the actually performed fragments is globally decreasing until generation 20. After this period, we can observe a clear tendency: the training distance decreases while the test distance does not decrease anymore. This is a situation of overfitting, which might be a consequence of the limited amount of training data.

6.2 Discussion of the results

We present a summary of the conclusions we were able to draw based on the runs presented below.

- EPGM and learning

First we can see that for all the experiments we presented, EPGM is able to evolve models which maximize the fitness function, and consequently learns aspects of the training data, independently of the type of prediction to provide. In a small-scale single regression experiment, we have informally compared the results provided by the best-of-run model with the predictions returned by the a Model Tree. It may be interesting to compare quantitatively the results of EPGM with the best performing approaches for comparable problems. However, we think that the strength of EPGM lies in enabling the modeling of tasks difficult to address with standard classification/regression techniques.

- EPGM and generalization

We have also shown in a larger-scale experiment that the evolution process tends to maximize the generalization accuracy of the models, especially when using a purely error driven fitness function. However, in the case of Experiment 3, we were not able to maximize the generalization accuracy. There are some reasons that can account for this. First, the last experiment we present is using a small database, from which it may be difficult to generalize complex predictions. The second possible reason lies in the fact that we used a small population size population size for this run, while the prediction space is extended (the **ERegValue-3** primitive has eight float-valued members and two boolean members).

Figure 6.7: Experiment 2. Tree size of the best-so-far model during the evolution (Whole data set, averaged on five cross validation runs). Dotted: Fitness 1, Plain: Fitness 2

Figure 6.8: Experiment 3. Average edit-distance of best-of-run model during the evolution (Performance Similarity-based fitness). Plain: training data, dashed: test data

- Cross validation

Evolutionary Computation is a stochastic process. In the case of modeling difficult tasks, it is perfectly plausible that EPGM fails in one run and succeeds in the next one. This work highlights the necessity of cross validation for characterizing the accuracy of this approach. This, however, leads to computational issues as described below.

- Impact of the population size

When dealing with simple experiments (e.g. Experiment 1) the choice of the population size is not crucial. However it becomes critical when addressing more complex problems such as Experiment 2 for the whole database or Experiment 3. In the former case, we have been able to grow models which exhibit good generalization (i.e. using the error-driven fitness measurement) only with a population size of 1000 individuals. Using smaller populations, the models often converge to a mere `ERegValue` primitive. In the latter case, using a population size of 200 individuals does not provide satisfactory generalization capabilities. Note that using the hybrid fitness function enables the use of smaller populations because the unsupervised component prevents the models to converge to a mere primitive. But, again, this latter fitness measurement does not yield acceptable generalization capabilities.

- Computational issues

A major issue in EPGM approach is the computational time required to evolve models. For instance, a five-fold cross validation run based on the whole database (Experiment 2) required more than 60 hours to be completed. A single run based on a small database involving the prediction of **ERegValue-3** primitives (Experiment 3) lasted more than 18 hours, which prevented us to complete a cross validation run on the whole database. This latter case can be explained because the fitness function based on melodic similarity involves an edit-distance computation, which is itself an expensive process. On the other hand we can note that the memory usage does not seem to be critically affected by the size of the database nor by the complexity of the prediction type. We will propose in next chapter some strategies for dealing with the computational bottleneck we are facing.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and work proposal

7.1 Summary of contributions

We have applied data mining techniques for inducing models able to represent some aspects of expressive music performance (i.e. type of performance events, characteristics of the performance events). To achieve this, we have used classification and regression techniques for modeling separately these aspects, and integrated the resulting models into an *aggregate of models*. As a proof of concept, we have designed a software tool for completing both performance rendering and explanation tasks. We have stressed the limitations of the resulting modeling approach, namely model inconsistency, lack of scalability, and lack of control. We have then suggested an alternative approach, called Evolutionary Population of Generative Models (EPGM). This approach was applied to a number of inductive performance modeling experiments ranging from simple regression tasks to complex tasks. This has led us to highlight the strengths and the weaknesses of the presented approach.

We will now present a work proposal aiming to refine our approach in several directions. We first propose some directions to be investigated in order to overcome the EPGM computational bottleneck we highlighted in previous chapter and suggest some general EPGM extensions. Then, we propose to extend our approach in the context of expressive performance modeling in order to consider a wider range of aspects involved in this phenomenon. This lead us to consider expressive performance modeling in a broader perspective, in which several computational models of human cognition would interact. Finally, we draw a summary of the research we have carried out

and presented in this document.

7.2 Refining EPGM

We propose here a set of work directions aiming to refine the EPGM approach. As mentioned above, a major current issue in the proposed approach is the computation time required to evolve models able to generalize well complex prediction tasks. We propose to investigate the following points.

- Working with smaller populations

We saw in the previous chapter that complex tasks could hardly be addressed by EPGM when working with small populations, however working with large populations is practically difficult due to the computation time required to evaluate a whole generation. We introduced an unsupervised fitness component that speeds up the learning process and enables the use of small populations. However the resulting models are too fitted to the training data. We need to devise and compare new unsupervised fitness components in order to speed up the learning process while sparing the generalization power of the resulting models. We also plan to incorporate Simulated Annealing [Kirkpatrick et al., 1983] ideas in the genetic search. This technique, by testing random mutations on individual solutions, introduces a decaying noise in the search and may enable to find useful solutions quicker.

- Relevant sampling

Another aspect of the presented EPGM approach is that each individual is evaluated iteratively on the *whole* training set, which makes the cost of the evaluation at least linearly dependent of the size of the training database. This yields expensive computations, even with the relatively small database we use in this work. We will devise sampling strategies for enabling the system to evaluate the models on relevant subsets of the training database while allowing the population of models to converge to useful solutions. Furthermore, the proposed sampling strategies will integrate knowledge regarding the structure of the training data.

- Setting a distributed framework

Overall, almost all the computation time needed to evolve models is spent in evaluating separately each model. Another way of overcoming the computational bottleneck lies in *distributing* the evaluation of models to a set of separate computers or processors. Several evolutionary framework provide distributed computation components (either client/server or peer to peer architectures). For instance Open Beagle features a client/server distributed component called Distributed Beagle, which architecture is shown in Figure 7.1. We plan to set up this distributed framework in order to increase available computational power, either with multiple desktop stations or with a cluster.

Figure 7.1: The Distributed Beagle architecture

We believe the directions proposed above can effectively reduce the computational issues we highlighted above. On the other hand, we plan to investigate the following extensions and refinements to the actual EPGM approach.

- Multiobjective optimization

In the Genetic Algorithm literature, a usual approach for integrating different measurements into a single fitness value lies in performing a weighted average (either arithmetic or geometric) of the different components. This is the approach we have followed so far. However, recent studies have shown the limitations of this approach. For instance, two components may be "antagonist" in the sense that any improvement

observed in one component would lower the other component measurement. In such case, it may be preferable to use multiobjective optimization strategies (see Zitzler and Thiele [1999]) in order to extract a *Pareto front*, i.e. a set of solutions which optimize the tradeoff between the distinct components of the fitness. This research direction will particularly benefit to expressive performance modeling where different aspects such as training and generalization accuracy on several expressive dimensions can be considered.

- Multiple prediction types

We plan to refine further our approach to enable the use of multiple prediction types simultaneously in the tree models. In the context of the prediction of performance events, this means that one leaf of the tree model could predict e.g. an ornamentation event and its characteristics while another leaf could predict e.g. a consolidation event. This way we would not have to devise compound prediction types such as the **ERegValue-3** primitive presented in Chapter 5, and we could easily add new possible performance events. We can implement this feature by giving all the possible prediction primitives a common type from the STGP point of view. In this case, the **ERegValue** random generator will be in charge of choosing which type of performance event has to be encapsulated in the **ERegValue** primitive.

- Towards models with state

As mentioned in the introduction, we have proposed in this work a feature-driven approach to performance modeling. That is, the predictions provided by the models are only function of the melodic context features, while the models should also have access to the past predictions they returned. We will investigate the modalities of considering both features and recent predictions in the decision making process.

We have presented in this section a two-fold research plan for refining the EPGM approach. First we proposed solutions to the computational bottleneck issue that would enable the system to learn faster and better. Additionally we proposed extensions to our approach that were motivated by our research on music performance modeling, but could potentially apply to other domains. We now present a proposal specifically oriented to music performance modeling.

7.3 Work directions specific to music performance modeling

We first present some extensions for refining our current music performance modeling approach. The following extensions can be investigated using the actual EPGM modeling approach provided that we resolve the computational issues we highlighted in previous chapter.

- Predict a wider range of expressive features

So far, we considered a limited amount of possible expressive features, namely the performance events presented in Chapter 1. From this viewpoint, we loose track of a larger repertoire of expressive gestures (especially the microstructure of the performance). Consequently, we will include intra-note features in our model: microtonal information (i.e. energy and pitch microstructure), timbral features (e.g. centroid shape). We are also interested in modeling transition features such as staccato and legato. Correspondingly we will integrate these features into an extended performance similarity measure, by adding new edit operations cost specific to these features.

- Generate new melodic representations

Also, an interesting work perspective is to devise a evolutionary melodic feature extractor that would coevolve with the performance model. Indeed, the melodic context of each note can be considered from several viewpoints, each one representing a certain level of analysis. For instance Conklin and Anagnostopoulou [2001] present relevant ideas to build melodic context features using a small set of “building blocks”. This is a promising work direction, because the outcome of the evolutionary process would be a set of models able to generalize the expressive behavior of the training excerpts along with a set of melodic features which are useful for characterizing the expressivity of a given performer.

- Hybrid fitness considering user feedback

We have devised so automatic fitness components for evaluating the accuracy our the evolved models. We propose to integrate an *interactive* fitness component in the evolution. This means that, at some

point, a user can choose which are the models corresponding best to its aesthetic preferences. This is also useful in order to discard models which produce false notes even if their global accuracy makes them well ranked. Evolutionary Computation is an idoneous framework for integrating such a user feedback, however it is known that evolution driven by interactive evaluation is a slow process. This is the reason why we plan to devise an hybrid fitness that would eventually call the user-driven component in order to prune the model search.

- Increase the amount of training data

We are aware that our database is relatively small and that much more data is needed to understand and model the complex music performance phenomenon. New methods for the acquisition of performance data from polyphonic recordings start to give interesting results. This would allow us to obtain data from commercial recordings and, consequently, to have access to a virtually infinite collection of performances. It is mandatory to build a representative performance database if we want to investigate thoroughly the generalization (from both statistical and musical point of view) power of the induced models.

On the other hand, we are interested in considering expressive music performance from a broader perspective. As mentioned in Chapter 1, this phenomenon involves a range of cognitive areas, therefore we should investigate the computational modeling of further aspects of human cognition and study whether such models can help us gaining further insights into music performance modeling. In Figure 7.2, we illustrate this idea. So far, we have only studied the score-driven contribution to music performance (marked in *italic*). However, all the components present in the figure may also play an important role and have to be investigated in the future.

7.4 Summary

We have investigated in this doctoral pre-thesis work inductive approaches for building computational models of music performances. Expressive music performance modeling is a particularly challenging area because it is an epiphenomenon involving several areas of human cognition and because few computational techniques (e.g. data mining) are effectively suitable for this

Figure 7.2: Computational models of areas involved in music performance

problem. We have first introduced this phenomenon in Chapter 1 from various viewpoints: musicology, psychology, brain science, cognitive science. We have then presented approaches to define music performance as a whole, or as a deviation from the score. In Chapter 2 we have presented the context of investigation and the past works aiming to build, either manually or automatically, computational models of performance. In Chapter 3, we have shown the various steps required to build an expressive performance database from monophonic recordings of jazz saxophone: feature extraction, segmentation and transcription, and finally alignment. In Chapter 4, we have used this database to induce a range of models intended to model several aspects of music performance. To achieve this, we have applied several well established data mining algorithms, either propositional or relational, to perform classification and regression tasks. Based on this we have devised a model aggregate in order to apply expressive transformations to inexpressive melodies. We have shown the limits of this approach, which are the following: model inconsistency, lack of scalability, and lack of control. To overcome these limitations, we have presented in Chapter 5 a new approach based on Evolutionary Computation (EC) entitled Evolutionary Population of generative Models (EPGM). Following we have given an overview of the EC field and its applications to music and learning. Then, we have developed a first instance of EPGM based on Strongly Typed Genetic Programming

(STGP) that enables to evolve population of models providing predictions of arbitrary types. In particular, we defined the primitives, terminals, genetic operators and fitness functions for this problem. We also devised a novel approach for evolving models by sequence similarity which fitness is based on edit-distance computation. In Chapter 6 we applied our approach to a range of expressive performance problems, ranging from small-scale single regression experiments to full-scale multivariate regression problems. We have shown our approach is promising and is suitable in some case for producing models able to generalize the training data. However, for being successful in terms of generalization accuracy, the approach needs to work with a population of individuals of significant size (e.g. 1000 individuals). In the case of using elaborate fitness functions, such as the similarity function based on edit-distance, this would require a massive use of computational resources. This led us to dress a proposal for overcoming this computational bottleneck. Apart from this, we have proposed extensions to our approach addressing an extended range of expressive performance dimensions in a unified way. We think the presented approach is scalable and general enough to address the computational modeling of tasks which have proved to be difficult to model with standard classification or regression approaches.

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Chapter 8

Appendix

As an addition to this doctoral pre-thesis report, we present in this appendix a description of the most relevant publications we have written in relation with the investigation presented here.¹ The publications presented below can be downloaded on the IUA web site (see footnote).

8.1 Publication Context

- Discovering Performance Transformation Rules from Saxophone Jazz Performances (2005). Rafael Ramirez, Amaury Hazan, Emilia Gómez and Esteban Maestre. *Journal of New Music Research*, 34(4), 319-330

We presented in this journal article the process of building the expressive performance database from acoustic recordings of jazz saxophone. We then applied Inductive Logic Programming in order to mine the resulting relational database, and extracted simple and general performance first order logic rules.

- A Tool For Generating And Explaining Expressive Music Performances Of Monophonic Jazz Melodies (2006). Rafael Ramirez, Amaury Hazan. *International Journal on Artificial Intelligence Tools*, 15(4). B. Manaris and P. Machado Eds.

We presented in this journal article the expressive performance rendering and explanation tool we presented in Section 4.6. This work led us

¹We refer to <http://www.iaa.upf.edu/mtg/publicacions.php> for a complete list of personal publications.

to investigate alternatives to model aggregation.

- **Modelling Expressive Music Performance: A Regression Tree Approach Based on Strongly-typed Genetic Programming (2006)**. Amaury Hazan, Rafael Ramirez, Esteban Maestre, Alfonso Perez and Antonio Pertusa. Proceedings of the Forth European Workshop on Evolutionary Music and Art (EvoMusArt 06), part of the European conference on Genetic Programming (EuroGP), Budapest, Hungary. Springer LNCS 3907.

In the conference paper which was published in the Springer Lecture Notes in Computer Science Collection, we set the basis of the EPGM theoretical framework by creating Strongly Typed Genetic Programming based regression trees. We apply the presented approach to a small database of expressive performance cases in order to predict the performed notes duration ratio.

- **Evolving Performance Models by Performance Similarity: Beyond Note-to-note Transformation (2006)**. Amaury Hazan, Marteen Grachten and Rafael Ramirez. Proceedings of the Sixth International Symposium on Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR 06), Victoria, Canada.

This conference paper introduces the similarity-based fitness measurement based on edit-distance, which was fit to human judgement. This enables to get rid of pairwise comparisons between the score and the target performances, and allows to model a range of performance events.